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Journal of Applied Studies in Language (JASL) published twice a year in June and December. JASL calls for papers (and reviewers) and book review in Linguistics and Language Teaching. **Linguistics**, including, but not limited to, Phonology, Morphology, Syntax, Semantics, Literature, Pragmatics, Discourse Analysis, Language Acquisition, Sociolinguistics and Psycholinguistics and **Language Teaching**, such as First Language and Second Language Teaching, and Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL).

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Preface

In the name God, the Compassionate the Merciful, who has given us, the authors and editors, an opportunity to disseminate the authors' researches through the Journal of Applied Studies in Language published by Politeknik Negeri Bali. We, the team of editors, of course appreciate all the authors who have submitted the research papers to publish in our journal. We always try hard to serve every author and their research papers, although we realize that it is not a simple task to do.

We really happy since we are able to publish twelve (12) manuscripts in Volume 1 Number 1, December 2017 on time based the schedule. In this first publication, Volume 1 Number 1, published in December 2017, the journal presents twelve (12) research papers. Eleven (11) papers are written by writers and researchers from outside the institution of the publisher where the journal is published. It means that the journal is able to invite 91.7% of the papers from outside of the institution of the publisher. Five papers talk about English teaching, three papers are about linguistics, two about morphology, one about phonology, and two papers are about literature and social culture.

The first paper is **Learners' models enhance the development of learners' reading and thinking strategies**. It is followed by the second research paper with the title **Grammar teaching at pre-service training program in Kampung Inggris (a case study on mastering system program)**. The third paper is **Development of Indonesian language book using Glasser model**. Then we present the fourth paper, **The application of generosity maxim: a case study in "Divergent" movie**. The fifth paper is **The importance of developing android-based Indonesian language dictionary for the blind (KABITUNA)**. The sixth paper is **The use of modality markers to perform hegemony politeness in using Balinese language: a case study on *Awig-awig***, and the seventh paper is **Phonological variation of Javanese in Kebumen district**. Then the eighth paper is **Analysis technique of translation and measurement shift (shifts) in the text of AXA Life contract Indonesia**. The ninth paper is **The Design and development of model of English training program for local community at rural tourism**. The tenth paper is **Codes mixing between buyers and mobile phone hackers in Bekasi, West Java**. The eleventh paper is **Existence of Acehnese expression in culture of Indonesian speech community**. The last or the twelfth paper is **Syntactical interference of Katigan language to Indonesian language in SMP Negeri 1 at Katingan Tengah regency of Central Kalimantan**.

Majid Wajdi
Editor Member

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Learners’ models enhance the development of learners’ reading and thinking strategies

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Abstract – This study was conducted to find the efficient way to teach academic reading skills to non-English department students at tertiary education. Based on the previous study, it was found that the students found difficulty in reading academic texts because of their limited vocabulary. Reading experts state that “good readers are good guessers” (Nation, 2002). Further, He claims that the strategies of guessing meaning from context is important strategy in reading. Considering these statements, this study investigated reading class by teaching the strategies of guessing meaning from context. Since this study was conducted to solve the students’ perceived problem when reading academic texts, it applied three-cycle qualitative inductive action research together with the students. These three cycles were: Cycle 1, the lecturer provided individual model of strategies, namely identifying parts of speech, finding clues from contexts, and identifying word parts; Cycle 2, the lecturer showed various models and gave practices; and Cycle 3, some selected students demonstrated their models to the class. Throughout this study, the students were encouraged to write journals explaining the strategies applied when they were guessing the meanings of words. The data was analyzed from the students’ journals collected at the end of each cycle. The results indicated that the students’ models were more efficient than the lecturer’s. Learning and showing the strategies of guessing words from context encouraged the students to develop their deep thinking strategies when reading academic texts. The focus of this paper is on the treatments to introduce the word guessing strategies to the students in brief.

Keywords: *reading strategies, guessing meaning from context, teaching strategies*

1. Introduction

English was a compulsory subject at tertiary education. Usually, the non-English department students had to learn English at least one semester. The 2016 curriculum run at Politeknik Negeri Bandung is still encouraged the non-English department students to learn English at least two semesters. English lecturers at these departments were often challenged by their students who usually did not have high motivation to learn English because the students usually learned English to improve their speaking skills. However, one of the institutional objectives was to develop students' academic reading skills. Therefore, English lecturers are advised to bridge these mismatched expectations.

When teaching a language, teachers are advised to think of when and how a language is acquired and learned. Some researchers (Krashen and Terrell, 2000) and (Nunan, 1994) distinguish between “acquiring” and “learning”. “Acquiring” is a subconscious process when the learners are picking up the language through rich exposure; while ‘learning’ is a conscious process when the learners are consciously picking and carrying out practices. The language learnt does not ‘turn into’ acquisition unless the input is comprehensible and practiced in a meaningful context (Krashen and Terrell, 2000) as cited in Nunan (1994) and Brown (1994). Learning will only take place when the matter to be learnt is meaningful to the learners (Hutchinson and Waters (1989). This will only take place when the matter to be learnt is interesting to the learners (Hutchinson and Waters (1989). Language teachers need to provide acquisition rich activities, meaningful contexts, and provide meaningful repetition through listening and reading before speaking and writing (Hadaway, Vardell and Young, 2002).

The challenge arises when the language learners do not live in the English speaking environment or they live at a distance from the target language community, such as learning English in Indonesia. However distant they are, language learners have similar learning process and purpose as those who learn the target language as their first language, namely for communicating ideas orally and in written. Since learning English in Indonesia only has limited time, the focus of teaching and learning English at tertiary education is mostly focused on improving academic reading skills. This is to prepare the students to enrich their majoring subjects by means of reading from various academic texts. Therefore, this study was focused and conducted in a reading class at a civil engineering department at Politeknik Negeri Bandung. The purpose of this study was to discover the efficient way to improve students' academic reading skills but at the same time to cater for the students' interests.

This study was conducted based on these claims: “good readers are good guessers” (Nation, 2002). Further, readers are constructing and guessing the meanings, and they read with a certain purpose (Nuttall, 1989). When guessing meanings, they apply all their prior language knowledge such as their large vocabularies, phonemic awareness, knowledge about text features, and a variety of strategies (Paris, Wasik and Turner, 1991) and knowledge about the world. In addition, Nation (2002) claims that the skills of guessing meaning from context are important skills in reading.

Therefore, this study attempted to develop students' reading strategies by means of developing the strategies to guess the meaning of new words encountered

from context (GMFC). This was to cater for the students' perceived problems, the limited vocabulary, and to improve the students' reading skills.

2. Method

This study was carried out to solve the students' perceived problems, namely limited vocabulary. It applied three-cycle qualitative inductive action research conducted together with the students as the stakeholders. The main characteristic of action research is the spiral activity consisting of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting (Stringer, 1996) as cited in Merawati (2003). The data were collected from students' journals at the end of each cycle. These journals contained the strategies applied when they were guessing the meanings of new words appeared in the provided texts.

3. Results and Discussion

This part explains the treatments, results, and discussion of the study briefly. The treatments were planned and conducted based on the results of students' open questionnaires and discussion with the students conducted at the previous studies (Merawati, 2010). They were conducted to solve the students' perceived problems i.e. limited vocabulary; and the results were derived from the data, in the form of students' journals collected at the evaluation stages at the end of each cycle.

The study had three cycles of treatments. The treatments of Cycle 1 consisted of five individual models run within four weeks. The first model was focusing on identifying the part of speech of words of a text. The students were encouraged to find the nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs or the contents words by means the word positions in sentences – as subjects, verbs, objects, adjectives, or adverbs (McComish, 1985). The second model was to find clues of deleted words from the nearest context to larger ones, namely words existed before and after the gaps and ones from other sentences. The third one was to demonstrate and practice mature guessing namely revising, refining and thinking critically. Then, the fourth model was to show guessing strategies using diagrams and other typography clues such as punctuations, bold, italic words, etc. Finally, the students were introduced the process of predicting the meanings of new words from the parts of the words, such as 'lighthouse' from "light + house", and 'remodeled' from 're + model + ed'. The materials used to introduce and practice these strategies were taken from various short simple authentic texts.

Cycle 2 treatments were carried out for seven weeks. They focused on practicing the process of guessing the meanings of unknown words whenever the students met new words in short authentic texts. Other strategies were also introduced i.e. activating the students' prior knowledge, identifying the semantic relation of words especially hyponyms and enlarging the readers' scope of textual context (Nation, 2002). In addition to give a lot of practices, the students were also encouraged to collaborate when guessing some new words in groups.

Cycle 3 treatments which ran for three weeks were to provide practices and allow the students to demonstrate their GMFC models. At the end of each class, some selected students reported the process of guessing to the class orally. At this cycle, the students had a lot of collaborative oral activities and they attempted to express their

logical reasons aloud by working in pairs or in small groups and presenting their strategies orally in front of the class (Nation, 2002). The reading materials were selected from various children encyclopedia. These materials were modified in such a way that the texts stimulated the students to guess purely unknown words and enlarge their textual scopes.

The treatments were evaluated by means of collecting students' journals at the end of each cycle. The improvements of guessing process were evaluated from students' abilities to make use of clues by identifying the words' parts of speech and finding clues from typography, word parts, and locations of the clues, expressing the meanings of unknown words, and monitoring the results of their guesses.

The results of the students' ability to identify the parts of speech of words showed that these students had some language knowledge, namely syntax, and structures (Mikulecky, 1990) so that they were able to construct meanings using bottom-up approach (Aebersold and Field, 1998). The students' ability to identify the part of speech developed from 54% at the end of Cycle 1, to 43% at the end of Cycle 2; however, at the end of Cycle 3, it was going up to 92%.

The students' abilities to find clues can be from word parts and word clues. Their abilities to find word parts developed from 48% at the end of Cycle 1, to 12% at the end of Cycle 2; however, it improved significantly to 62% by the end of Cycle 3. Whereas word clues are function words such as 'or', 'for example', 'to be' and other phrases such as 'called', 'in other words'. The students' abilities to find word clues developed from 11% at the end of Cycle 1, and slightly increased to 20% at the end of Cycle 2; and finally it reached to 21% by the end of Cycle 3. These abilities reflected that when reading, the students or the readers were not focusing on each word but they also looked at the pictures' notes, signaling words and analyzed words.

The locations of context clues show the scope of contexts. This indicates that when reading, students are not focusing on each single word, so that they are able to link ideas and construct meanings from various clues scattered in different places in the texts. This also proved that the students do not read texts linearly but they look the words backwards and forwards and elaborate various tactics. The development of students' scope of context was started from reading linearly at the end of Cycle 1, their scope of contexts was very limited; it was only 1% taken from the paragraph before the new words. However, at the end of Cycle 3 their scope of contexts increased to 31% clues taken from the previous paragraphs and 18% of clues taken from the paragraphs after the new words. In other words, the students' scopes of context were enlarged and they applied more strategies than at Cycle 1.

The ability to express the meaning of new words indicated the students' abilities to construct meanings of the new words based on the clues in the texts and other associations built as a result of reading the texts. This process reflected the students' deep and critical thinking, because they attempted to integrate various aspects of the texts such as the topic of the texts, the ideas of the paragraphs; then, they link and check their guessing their prior knowledge and experiences.

The 3 cycles of treatments developed the students' ability to describe the meaning from 11% at Cycle 1 and 2 to 23% at Cycle 3. The students were also getting flexible by providing multiple guesses. This flexibility improved from 5% at Cycle 1, then 9% at Cycle 2, and finally increased to 11% at Cycle 3. This indicated that they might need to revise the meanings or ideas later, as it was claimed in (Paris, Wasik and Turner, 1991). The result of analyzing the students' guessing process from their

journals indicated that at the end of Cycle 1 and 2, none students did monitoring and checking the results of their guesses. After some students provided models in front of the class in Cycle 3, the number of students who did this process increased from 0% to 24%. This showed that the students were able to think deeply and moved towards better readers because they applied more strategies when guessing.

The results of analyzing the students' guessing process written in their journals at the end of each cycle indicated that the number and the types of strategies applied by the students were significantly increased. This reflected that the students reading skills improved that good readers construct meanings maturely and always monitor their comprehension; they are always ready to refine and revise and evaluate their ideas in (Paris, Wasik and Turner, 1991).

Comparing the results of those three cycles, the result indicated that after some selected students, either the good or the limited ones, gave models in front of the class for three weeks, these students' strategies developed significantly. The models demonstrated the strategies slower and simpler, and they spoke slower and explained the strategies in simple words and sentences. The language used and the strategies demonstrated by the students were at the level of 'comprehensible input' (Krashen and Terrell, 2000) so that those strategies were digestible. Learners' motivation was developed because they were able to practice to speak naturally by expressing what they thought and experienced orally. As a result, the other students were willing and able to imitate and apply more various strategies to guess the meanings of new words from contexts.

4. Conclusion

When teaching English, lectures had to be able to bridge the mismatched expectations. One of the institutional objectives was to develop students' reading skills. On the other hand, the students wanted to be able to speak English fluently; and they were reluctant to read because of their limited vocabulary. Then, the lecturer developed the students' reading skills through developing students' compensation strategies namely guessing meaning from context. To cater for the students' expectation, the lecturer developed the students reading strategies and skills by integrating the four language skills. The students were encouraged to read and guess the important new words encountered in texts. They had to write what they thought by writing the strategies applied in their journals. Finally, they had to report and demonstrate their strategies orally in front of the class. Comparing the strategies written in the students' journals collected at the end of each cycle, it was found that the students' strategies developed significantly after the models were presented by some students. This indicated that the students' models enhanced the development of reading and thinking strategies.

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Grammar teaching at pre-service training program in *Kampung Inggris* (a case study on mastering system program)

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Abstract – *Kampung Inggris* is a very popular English learning area as there are many English courses with various programs are offered. Mastering System is a pre-service training program at one of the leading courses in *Kampung Inggris*. They are devoted exclusively to graduates or instructors interested in teaching in formal or non-formal schools. The purpose of this research is to reveal the process of teaching Grammar on Mastering System program. This research is a qualitative research using case study design. Data was collected through interviews, observation, and document analysis. There were a total of 3 teachers and 5 students interviewed. Observations were made to find out how teachers and students perform the learning and teaching process in the Grammar class as well as outside the classroom. Documents used in the form of field notes, transcripts recording interviews, brochures, schedules and subject matter. Document analysis was done by organizing data, coding and reducing, and representing. Based on data analysis, it can be concluded that Grammar teaching process in MS program is carried out in two activities, namely Grammar class and Study Club. In classroom learning, instructors apply the PBL (Problem-Based Learning) method. In Study Club activities, teaching is done in tutorial with the delivery of material using CTL (Communicative Language Teaching). The purpose of Grammar teaching is for MS students to be able to improve Grammar understanding through the cases found in the giving of tutorials to juniors. In addition, MS students can practice firsthand how Grammar's teaching process before going to school. From the results of interviews and observations obtained the conclusion that the involvement of students actively in learning Grammar able to create effective learning.

Keywords: *grammar teaching, mastering system program, Kampung Inggris*

1. Introduction

Having the ability to speak English is a necessity for people who want to develop themselves because English is a communication tool that can be used universally. It is stated that English is a worldwide language spoken throughout all parts of life such as in the arts, sciences, humanities, travel and the social sciences. In other words, English influences human development from various aspects of life (Astrid, 2011).

In Indonesia, English learning has been started since elementary school. Some kindergartens even have started to be introduced the subject. However, from year to year the success of English language learning in high school still not satisfy the parents, professionals and lecturers when he entered the lecture bench (Richards and Schmidt, 2002). The main problem in learning English is that students have less mastery over English grammar or Grammar, especially on how to construct sentences, how to use appropriate verbs and verbs according to time changes (Astrid, 2011). From the background, researchers interested in knowing how to teach a good grammar to be mastered by students easily and quickly.

In the process of learning English, grammar has a very important role to support the four basic skills of English Speaking, Reading, Listening and Writing. It is assumed that a good Grammar's ability will affect in English language skills such as meaning or communication. This is mentioned that "Grammar and vocabulary play key-roles in the four language skills to create and Achieve communicative activities" (Kolawole, 1998). Grammar and vocabulary play a key role in the four language skills to create and achieve communicative activity. This is corroborated by Prihatini (2014) that in a communicative approach, Grammar is considered the language usage which is the foundation for communicating.

In general, Grammar is described as a language structure and the way in which language parts such as words and phrases are combined in sentences so as to produce meaning and function in the language system.

Grammar is a description of the structure of a language and the way in which linguistic units such as words and phrases are combined to produce sentences in the language. It usually takes into account the meanings and functions these sentences have in the overall system of the language. It may or may not include the description of the sounds of a language (Kolawole, 1998).

Grammar has and still holds an important position in language teaching. Today, researchers no longer focus on the necessity of grammar (Astrid, 2011). However, their current concern is what teachers need to direct the attention of learners to understand grammatical rules in meaningful context and natural situations. It was reported that "recent research studies have found that grammar teaching is essential since it enables students to attain high levels of proficiency in both accuracy and fluency" [5] Recent research has found that Grammar teaching is very important because it allows students to attain a high level of proficiency in both accuracy and fluency of language. In addition, it was reinforced that "students' explicit knowledge

of grammar will develop their communicative skills, enhance (Asmara, 2013) their language proficiency and enable them to edit or monitor their written and spoken work (Asmara, 2013). Students' knowledge of a good Grammar develops communicative skills, improves language skills and allows them to edit or check their writing and speaking.

Grammar is not only taught in schools but also in institutions of English courses. English course institution is one of the units of non-formal education that aims to develop the potential of learners in the mastery of English outside of formal education. The 2003 law number 20 on the National Education System article 26, paragraph 4 states that "The non-formal education unit consists of courses, training institutions, study groups, community learning center and majors, and similar educational units"

Article 26, paragraph 7 states that "Courses and training are held for people who need knowledge, skills, life skills, and attitudes to develop themselves, develop professions, work, independent business, and / or continue their education to a higher level. The regulation explains that courses and training in Indonesia are conducted for people who need knowledge, skills, life skills, and attitudes to self-development, professional development, employment, self-employment, and continuing their education to a higher level.

In addition, many people who choose to study English in the course as a support in formal education due to several factors such as lack of time to learn and less effective method of learning in school that makes them motivated to take English courses. Many people find it difficult to learn English because there are many problems such as lack of teaching time, ineffective teaching methods and lack of qualified faculty (Yusuf, 2010). It is reinforced by Yusuf (2010) that there are three causes that influence student learning: talent (ability, development and motivation), direction (strata / level of education and overall quality of experience), and circumstances around (home, peers, classroom conditions and television broadcasts).

Kampung Inggris is one of the most famous English learning places in Indonesia because there are many institutes of English language courses offering programs. In improving English proficiency, *Kampung Inggris* has many facilities that support learning book stores, public libraries, internet cafes and the number of temporary residences provided by local residents. In general, English courses in English Village are divided into two types. The first is focus on speaking teaching and the second is the focus on Grammar learning. But from the researcher's observation, the first type has a larger number of enthusiasts than the second type.

Of the many English courses available in *Kampung Inggris*, there is one course that offers a different program that is the Mastering System (MS) program which is a Pre-service training for English instructor program where the program is intended for graduate courses to better prepare to be a language teacher English either in formal or non formal school. This attracts researchers because pre-service training programs are very important in preparing them before entering the real learning process. Pre-service training gives prospective teachers actual classroom conditions

and estimates and prepares the things they need to have an effective teaching-learning process. It was also conveyed by ^[9]:

Pre-service teacher training is a program to develop teacher's competence by providing teachers-to-be with large portion of basic competencies of instructional strategies in training may help them to understand educational strategies, philosophical thoughts, psychological approaches, teaching methods and instructional techniques to uplift the professional competency and skills in real environment.

The above statement explains that pre-service teacher training is a program to improve teacher competence by providing teacher candidate with basic competence in giving instructional strategy so that it can help them to understand education strategy, philosophical thinking, psychological approach, teaching method and instructional technique to improve competence and professional skills in real learning environments.

Based on the above explanation, the researcher is interested to know more about Grammar teaching on Mastering System Program by considering the teaching method or technique used. In addition, researchers wanted to know whether the method or technique used was effective for Grammar teaching in MS programs.

2. Method

This research is a descriptive qualitative research using case study design. They explain that one type of descriptive qualitative research is in the form of research by method or case study approach (Case Study) is an intensive, detailed and in-depth study of an organism (individual), institution or symptom with a narrow area or subject. According to ^[13] case studies are used as a comprehensive exploration of the various aspects of a person, a group, an organization, a program or a societal situation that is researched, sought, and examined as deeply as possible.

Based on the above description it can be concluded that the case study design used in this study aims to understand the phenomenon of Grammar Teaching in the MS Program, where the same program has not been implemented in other courses. Data were collected through interviews, observation, and document analysis. Interviews were used in order to find data related to research focus. Subjects were the respondents for the interviews of 3 teachers and 5 students. Observations were made to find out how teachers and students perform the learning and teaching process in the Grammar class as well as outside the classroom. Documents used in the form of field notes, transcripts recording interviews, brochures, schedules and subject matter. Document analysis is done by organizing data, coding and reducing, and representing.

3. Results and Discussion

The Mastering System (MS) program is an extra program with 3 months study time consisting of 2 months for theory and 1 month for field practice. Through the results of document analysis in the form of subject schedules obtained information that there are Grammar classes are held 4 times a week from Monday to Thursday with a duration per meeting for 1.5 hours starting from 12:30 to 02:00. From the results of classroom observations and interviews with students obtained information that Grammar class is integrated with Study Club activities conducted every Monday-Thursday at 07.00-11.20 or precisely before Grammar class is implemented. This was told by the Grammar instructor, T1:

I love the description of MS. Gini, they were morning at 4:30 to 7 o'clock with Mr. Y, well after that their Study Club. Well, they've been in *** it's absorbing, not transferring so. Well from their Study Club for example there are difficulties such as editorial, language, explanation and so forth. That means when there are unpredictable questions before and so that's my job in class.

From the above explanation, it can be concluded that Grammar and Study Club classes are two integrated Grammar teaching facilities where Grammar subject teachers are tasked to help MS students complete the difficulties found in the Study Club. In detail, the activity description is described as follows.

3.1 Grammar Class

Based on the results of observation and interviews, it is learned that the learning in the Grammar class applies the PBL (Problem-Based Learning) method where the focus of learning is on the discussion of problems that arise in the Study Club activities. Problems or problems are then discussed and solved in classroom meetings. It was pointed out that "PBL as" a curriculum model is designed around real life problems that are ill structured, open ended or ambiguous" ^[10]. PBL is a curriculum model designed about real-life issues that are structured, and are not limited or ambiguous. Furthermore, he explains that "PBL engages students in intriguing real and relevant intellectual inquiry and allow them to learn from these life situations" ^[10]. PBLs engage students in generating curiosity through real and relevant questions and and letting them learn from real life situations.

Classroom activities begin with reading Basmallah as an opening, reviewing the material given at the previous meeting, then discussing the problems students face with their Grammar teaching in the Study Club.

For example we have our problem story to the teacher this problem like this, this problem like this, when children *** and *** love question to us but we still need reference from there we directly asked to the teacher that is T1, T1

immediately ordered to open the page book, menu like this, the title like this, study, like that. (S1)

So go in my class, I was the task wait for the ball only. Son asked what, today there is a problem what about Grammar, now that. Oh yes this, sir there is a question like this, there they bring a book pack, but how come. That's it. Well I love the explanation to be transferred tomorrow. (T1)

From the above explanation it is concluded that in the Grammar class, students convey the problems that occur to be solved together with the instructor or his friend. As already stated in the previous statement, usually the problems that arise about editorial, language, explanation and so forth. Instructors provide solutions by asking students to read books that can be used to answer problems that arise. By providing some reference books, instructors or instructors have a goal to motivate students to want to learn more about Grammar. This is also conveyed by T1 "Motivate them to want to open the book, want to read so. And mostly I give the names of books to buy. So recommend some books (Grammar) that can provide a solution. "

Furthermore, T1 says that some of the Grammar books that are referenced are Practical English Usage by Michael Swan, Understanding and Using English Grammar by Betty Schramper Azar, Living English Structure by William Stannard Allen, and Terakir Let's Write English by George E. Wishon & Julia M Burks. Each book has its own role such as Practical English Usage related to Preposition and Conjunction. Living English Structure is more to structure with simple materials for sentence analysis, such as Question Tags. Understanding and Using English Grammar contains more Grammar material as a whole but is generalized. T1 rated Betty's book as a counterweight for using American English where the average Grammar book uses British English. The last one is Let's Write English regarding Phrases such as Compound Complex Sentence or Pre-modifier and Post-modifier, Determiner, and more.

By using the PBL method, the learning process in the Grammar class is more centred on the students than the instructor or instructor (student-centred learning), where the instructor acts as a facilitator during the activities and the students have more active roles during the learning process. As a facilitator, the instructor plays a role in enabling the situation, which enables students to play a role in activities and discuss the material. In this case, students do more practice than learning theory, especially MS program is a pre-service training program focused on teaching practice, not theory. S2 said that "For the method here it's like that teacher more guides us. So between the theory and practice that his presentation is higher practiced. So we are not made dizzy by theory, we better understand it to practice directly "

Furthermore, after the questioning of the problem is resolved, the lesson proceeds by discussing the materials to be given to the Study Club tomorrow and what methods students can use during teaching to make the teaching process work effectively. ^[10] Defines the PBL as ... the learning which results from the process of working towards the understanding of or the resolution of, a problem. PBL is a

learning that results from the process of understanding and resolution of a problem. From the activities in the classroom, students not only learn to understand the material but also the methods to solve the problem.

3.2 Study Club

This activity begins with the division of learning and teaching groups where MS students as instructors and junior students from the two underlying courses as students. Grammar teaching is done by way of tutorial where every single MS student guiding 7-10 younger class. On Saturday morning, a briefing for Study Club and Night Speaking was conducted from 09.30—11.00 to prepare the activity. The purpose of the Study Club is as a teaching practice before MS students go to schools where they will conduct an Outdoor Class Training or Field Training Practice in the 3rd month. In addition, the Study Club activity is also aimed at empowering so that MS students are able to measure the extent of Grammar ability that has been mastered. This is conveyed by teacher T1 "At least this as a medium to maximize because they teach the Study Club is a mirror to them that this improve your ability.

For junior students, this activity is intended that they can recall the Grammar material they have just acquired in class because the material given in the Study Club activity is determined by Grammar teacher in the MS class who also teach Grammar in their program, as stated by S3.

If in Study Club we learn to teach to our sisters about Grammar materials. Usually the material taught the material they just got in class. Why is it that determines the topic of our teacher Grammar, because T1 also teaches in ***, ***, and ***, he better understand what material is appropriate to be delivered.

Based on observations and interviews, MS students delivered materials using the CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) method where students and instructors discussed so enthusiastically. The CLT is based on the belief that language learning is not only determined by how to teach certain aspects of the language but is pursuing various exercises that provide opportunities for students to develop their language skills (Astrid, 2011). It is seen when in Study Club, MS students give freedom to the junior to ask and discuss. The duration of time required by each group is about 20 minutes. This is conveyed by T2 who also served as director of the Study Club. "So the first step we give an explanation, about its function, type of tenses, and we must enter the pattern. Then more examples to practice such as conversation."

In this activity, MS students use teaching media such as drawing or using games to make the learning atmosphere more interesting and easy in delivering the material. Teaching techniques obtained on Quantum Teaching subjects, while for the types of games obtained on the subject Games. This was revealed by S2.

So, to prepare the material yes the way that's how the game is given, or when ***, ***, whose name is human when only given the full material it was impressed bored so that we are here taught like that too. So we MS is more not

emphasized actually but more taught to be a teacher than to be taught, so why more practice, continue to practice right away.

In the Study Club, Grammar learning is felt to be very effective by MS students. This is stated by S4 students "If here the management of KBM time is very effective. Suppose that in one meeting there is an opening, content, so effective management when we discuss the content, when we share together, question and answer in the meeting really effective. "Students assume with the management of time KBM is structured and the application of CLT method on Study Club activities, able to create effective Grammar learning.

4. Conclusion

Based on the above explanation, the involvement of students actively in learning Grammar where student-centered learning applied as a learning technique is an effective way of teaching Grammar. The Problem-Based Learning method is an appropriate method especially for prospective English instructors before they dive into the real world of teaching. With this method prospective instructors can measure the extent to which the material they have mastered so that it can continue to learn from the problem solving that occurred. By applying the CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) method and the implementation of the Study Club tutorial program, students are able to absorb material quickly because of the intensive interaction between teachers and students.

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Development of Indonesian language book using Glasser model

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Abstract – This study aims to describe the process of developing teaching materials by using Glasser model in the Indonesian language course in FKIP UMSU. The sample of the research is 34-second semester A morning students in the Study Program of Language and Literature of Indonesia, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Muhammadiyah, Sumatera Utara. The questionnaire instrument was used to determine the student's response and activeness to the developed teaching material, the observation sheet used to know the condition of the students in the learning process, and the validation sheet instrument used for the development of teaching materials based on SAP using Glasser model. The result of descriptive research on student's response shows that 100% of students were happy about the teaching materials of Bahasa Indonesia (Teaching Materials, Guided Exercises and Lecture Strategies) and 91.66% of students think that the teaching materials are new to them. After using the teaching materials developed by the researcher and following the teaching and learning activities, students (100%) are interested in following the next lesson, the readability of the language of the learning material is easy to understand (91.66%) and the guidance given by the lecturer is clear (100%). While the self-employed activity is fun for students (91.66%). Students activity in learning activities was shown by their involvement in problem solving, his involvement in carrying out learning tasks, assessing his ability, digging and developing his own knowledge. Based on the validation sheet on the test of learning result 1 obtained information that from the 3 learning objectives formulated in SAP I and SAP II there is 1 learning objectives that have not yet completed. Based on the results of descriptive analysis of the test results of learning 2 it was obtained that the 3 learning objectives formulated in SAP III and SAP IV was finished learning objective.

Keywords: *learning material development, glasser model*

1. Introduction

One of the causes why the quality of education in Indonesia is still very low being compared with other countries in the world is the process of learning that took place at the university. It has not been done pursuant to the nature of learning. The role of lecturers is still so dominant that learning is still centered on lecturers. Such a process resulted in students tend to be lazy to follow the activities of teaching and learning in the classroom and often not to follow the eyes of the course and even just leave the absent to friends. So students will be difficult to push their skills and not train themselves to think how to acquire knowledge because they are accustomed to just receiving information.

Based on the existence of the interaction differences, the learning activities can be done by using various learning patterns. With the implementation of the learning pattern is expected to bring changes that shifted the role of lecturer as a transmitter of information and is no longer the only source of learning in learning activities. Broadly speaking, many major obstacles in the achievement of learning outcomes that are identified are the understanding of teachers about meaningful and holistic learning is still low so that students still learn knowledge separated, lecturers have not utilized the potential of the environment as a medium and learning resources, and learning systems tend to be monotone.

One effort that can be done to overcome the above problems is that lecturers must be smart in using the learning model. Learning model can be used as a pattern of choice. Lecturers choose the appropriate learning model and efficient to achieve educational goals. Glasser model is the simplest model. It only describes a design or development of learning. Glasser model can be tried during teaching and learning process and to know the result of student learning in Indonesian language course. So in this research the researchers want to explain the process of developing teaching materials by using Glasser model in Indonesian Language course in FKIP UMSU.

2. Method

The research was conducted at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education of Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra, which is located on Jalan Kapten Mukhtar Basri Number 3 Medan. The sample of the research was 34-second semester students of A Pagi Program of Language and Literature Education of Indonesia. The method used is descriptive quantitative. Questionnaires, observation sheets and validation sheets are used as research instruments. Questionnaires were used to find out the responses and activities of the students to the teaching materials developed, the observation sheet used to obtain data about the condition of the students in the learning process, while the validation sheet was used for the development of teaching materials based on SAP using Glasser model.

3. Results and Discussion

The teaching materials developed are Indonesian language teaching materials. Each subject contains learning activities to be undertaken by students who adopt researchers from the Glasser model. Expert validation results are shown as in the following table.

Table 3.1 Teaching Material Validation Result

Aspect of Assessment	Expert Validation Results						
	I			II			
							4
Beginning Part							
1. In the teaching materials there is a title							✓
Content Part							
2. List the basic competency standards and competencies to be achieved							✓
3. Loading learning objectives in accordance with SK and KD.							✓
4. Contains achievement indicators of SK and KD.							✓
5. Contains material description in accordance with SK and KD							
6. Load examples of problems and solutions that match the Glasser model.							
7. Loading practice questions							✓
Final Part							
8. Contains summaries/ conclusions and bibliography							✓
Contents							
9. Material supports KD achievement							✓
10. Contents context facilitates Glasser Model							✓
11. Context content facilitates learners to learn math skills							✓
12. Material truth							✓
13. Presenting problems to facilitate mathematical ability							
Language							
14. The grammatical truth corresponds to the Enhanced Spell							✓
15. Conformity of sentences with the level of development of learners							
16. Guidance clarity							
17. Eligibility as completeness of learning							✓

Description 1: less, 2: enough; 3: good; 4: very good

From the validation of teaching materials that have been obtained shows good and very good category for 15 aspects. From the assessment sheet there are also general

notes and conclusions given by experts. Based on the records of the experts have been revised as shown in the following table.

Table 3.2 Revised Teaching Materials

Before Revision	After Revision
Do not make sub subject	Sub subject has been made
In Writing a foreign language is not tilted	Each foreign language term is skewed
The sample matter has not been drawn from the material discussed	Replaced with the corresponding material
For each chapter use roman numerals	Replaced by using Arabic numerals for each chapter

Observations on student activities during teaching and learning activities are expressed as percentages, as in Table 3.3 below.

Table 3.3 Percentage of Student Activities during Teaching and Learning Activities

No.	Activities Observed	SAP I (%)	SAP II (%)	SAP III (%)	SAP IV (%)	Average (%)
1.	Observing	10	8	6	7	7,75
2.	Explanations	10	14	10	12	11,5
3.	Answer the questions	15	16	18	16	16,25
4.	Learn the teaching materials	40	35	40	35	37,5
5.	Discuss/ conduct guided exercises	20	20	20	20	20,00
6.	Presents the results of group discussions in front of the class	5	7	6	10	7
7.	Writing (relevant to KBM)	0	0	1	0	0,25
	Behavior that is not					

	relevant to KBM					
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The table above shows that the most prominent activities conducted during the teaching and learning activities are discussing and conducting guided exercises in groups (37.5%). Next is presenting the results of the discussion in front of the class (20%) and studying the 16.25% teaching materials. Behavior incompatible with KBM is almost non-existent (0.25).

Questionnaires about student responses to Indonesian language teaching materials using the Glasser model were distributed at the end of the fourth meeting on a limited trial. This instrument is filled by students without a name so that the result is more objective. It is briefly presented in the following table.

Table 3.4 Percentage of Student Response to Indonesian Language Materials by Using Glasser Model

No.	Students Response to Teaching Materials	Response	Average (%)
1.	Teaching materials	Exciting	100%
		New	100 %
2.	Readability of teaching materials	Easy	91,66%
3.	language	Yes	100%
4.	Interest to follow the next lecture	Clear	100%
5.	Lecturers' guidance in lectures	Exciting	91,66%
	Self-training activities		

The table above shows that 100% of students are happy with Indonesian Language (Material, Guided and Lecture) and 91.66% of students are of the opinion that the teaching materials are new to them. After using the teaching materials developed by the researcher and following the teaching and learning activities, students (100%) are interested in following the next lesson, the readability of the language of the learning material is easy to understand (91.66%) and the guidance given by the lecturer is clear (100%). While the self-employed activity is fun for students (91.66%).

In limited trials, there were two Trial Lectures Unit tested. In these two SAPs, discussed in Bahasa Indonesia materials. The lectures for the two teaching materials were conducted in four meetings. Meetings I and II examine the History and Development of Indonesian Language and the Indonesian Language Variety is reviewed at meetings III and IV. Test Results Learning is given at the end of the second meeting and the test of learning result II is given at the end of the meeting to IV. Learning result test I is used to measure the ability of students in understanding the History and Development of Indonesian Language includes indicators: (1) explain the development of Indonesian, (2) describes the position, and (3) explains the function of the Indonesian language. While the test of learning result II is used to measure the ability of students in understanding the Indonesian Variety, namely: can

use the variety of spoken and written language in context. The test of this learning result in the form of description. This test can also measure the high level of thinking skill. In order for this test properly fulfill its function then done content validation. To ensure the validity of the test, a table of specifications relating the learning objectives to the items is specified. The following table shows the completeness of the test results on a limited trial.

Table 3.5 Complete Test of Learning Outcomes I Trial I

No.	Learning Objectives	Question number	Completeness $p \geq 0,85$
1.	Explain the development of Indonesian language,	1a	Completed
2.	Explain the position,	1b	Completed
3.	Explaining the function of the Indonesian language	1c	Not completed

From the table above can be seen that the objectives of learning 1 and 2 are formulated in SAP for a limited trial by using Indonesian language learning material to complete. As for the third learning does not achieve mastery.

Table 3.6 Complete Test of Learning Result II Trial I

No.	Learning Objectives	Question number	Completeness $p \geq 0,85$
1	What is the prominent difference between the verbal and the written variety of a language?	1a	Completed
2	What do you think about standard language and non-standard language?	1b	Completed
3	Try to note the sentences below. Is the sentence smart or not? If it is not a smart sentence, try to fix the sentence! a) Before acting, the leader of the famous bank tried to approach the kinship. b) He received twenty-five thousand from us	1c	Not completed

From the table above can be seen that the objectives of learning 1 and 2 conducted on a limited trial by using teaching materials to achieve mastery. As for the third learning does not achieve mastery.

The result of descriptive analysis on student's response shows 100% of students are happy about the teaching materials of Bahasa Indonesia (Teaching Materials, Guided Instruction and Lecture Strategy) and 91.66% of students think that the material is new for them.

After using the teaching materials developed by the researchers and participating in the teaching and learning activities, students (100%) are interested in following the next lesson, the readability of the learning material is easy to understand (91.66%) and the guidance given by the lecturer is clear (100%). While the self-employed activity is fun for students (91.66%).

Student attitudes will appear in the learning process such as feelings of pleasure or displeasure, likes or dislikes of the process. Something that gives rise to pleasure tends to make the student want to continue doing it. The desire to follow the next lesson will affect the efficiency of the learning process.

Student activity in learning activities is shown by his involvement in problem solving, his participation in carrying out learning tasks, and assessing his ability. The quality of student learning achievement is shown by changes in knowledge, attitude and behavior. Active involvement of students means that students not only receive lecture materials given by the lecturer, but also involved in the discovery of knowledge. Students explore and develop their own knowledge. Lecture outcomes in addition to increasing knowledge but also thinking skills.

The teaching materials used in the lectures are arranged chronologically, by topic or category from theory to application or vice versa or based on the improvement of skill or complexity. It should be remembered that a structure that seems logical and clear to an expert may not be the best way for new student learning in the field. From a student's point of view, they may choose course material on topics that will generate confidence and interest in the material being studied. The students tend to be more motivated to work hard when they are successful at the beginning of the course and when they can connect new material with something they already know. Careful planning is needed because students are not automatically able to connect new information they know.

When analyzed data on the results of tests I and II in a limited trial, the goal of learning achievement of 75% of all learning objectives provided. Imagination of learning objectives, when viewed from the readiness of students, most likely the students have not been conditioned by learning with Glasser model. Another possibility is that students are not active in group work. Dubinsky (in Arnawa) states that when something is repeated and students reflect on the repetition, the action be a process, that is internal construction made by doing the same action, but now not directed by stimulus from the outside. Students who have constructed the process for a concept can describe or even reverse the steps of the transformation without actually doing it.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research results can be drawn conclusion as follows. First, Indonesian textbook using Glasser model can train students to think quickly. Second, Indonesian textbook using Glasser model can train students more creative because dealing directly with the problem; Third, Indonesian textbook using Glasser model can be students who do not understand the lessons can be assisted by their group friends and teachers; and the last one, Indonesian textbook using Glasser model can make students more easy to repeat lessons at home because students can directly come into contact with the object lesson.

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The application of generosity maxim: a case study in “Divergent” movie

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Abstract – Maxim is general principle which is thought to underlie the efficient use of language. This research was conducted to find out the existence of the generosity maxim applied by the characters in “Divergent” movie and the factors which caused the characters applying the maxim in their utterances throughout the movie. Data of the research was utterances used in the movie. The data was identified by using theory of maxim (Leech, 1983) to see if it merely applied the maxim of generosity and what factors influenced it use in the data. The data were analyzed by using the theory of politeness maxim proposed by Leech (1983) and the statements about factors that influence the application of politeness maxims proposed by Holmes (2001). The result analysis was described descriptively. Documentation and observation methods are applied in collecting the data. The result showed that the application of the generosity maxim existing in “Divergent” movie and the factors influencing the application of the maxim in this movie are gender and context of situation. The factors which most frequently influenced the application of the generosity maxim in the movie is the context of situation, and the factor which least frequently influenced the application of the maxim is gender.

Keywords: *politeness, generosity, maxim, factor*

1. Introduction

Communication is very important in human life. Communication can be defined as the process of transmitting information and common understanding from one person to another (Luxenburg, 2010). An information can be transmitted or delivered orally or in writing. People create languages, gestures, and manuscript to deliver what they want to tell to the others. However, people have a certain culture to be followed as general agreement in their society. One part of that culture is to differentiate good attitudes from the bad ones. So is in speaking. In conversation, people should speak in a way that is considered as the good one to avoid conflict with the others. People should be polite in communicating and interacting with others; in behavior, attitude, and in way of speaking as well.

Politeness means behavior that is respectful and considerate of other people (<http://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=politeness>). In social life, politeness should be applied to make and maintain good relationship with other people. Politeness is described as a genuine desire to be pleasant to others, or as underlying motivation for an individual's linguistic behavior (Thomas, 1995). By being polite, people will be able to minimize the probability of conflict with others. They will respect each other and there will be no one being offended. By applying politeness in everyday life, harmony in society should be able to be maintained. Politeness is important to make all the parties in a conversation feel comfortable to each other. By applying politeness, they will be able to create a good and comfortable situation when they are having a talk in, for example, a discussion, a meeting, a family gathering, a community gathering, and all forms of interactions with the other people.

Politeness applied in a society has to be in line with the culture of the society itself, but mostly politeness exists and is applied in every culture around the world. Politeness is realized by people in a region by following particular norms in line with the culture where they live, but generally, the purpose of politeness is to maintain harmony in a society. Politeness seeks opportunity for comity (Leech, 1983). The term "comity" is defined as friendly social atmosphere or social harmony (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/comity>).

Leech proposed a theory of politeness namely politeness principle. This theory will be applied in analyzing the data in this research. Politeness principle might be formulated as minimizes the expression of impolite beliefs and maximizes the expression of polite beliefs (Leech, 1983). Politeness principle is divided into six maxims, such as the tact maxim, the generosity maxim, the approbation maxim, the modesty maxim, the agreement maxim, and the sympathy maxim. This research is focused only to Generosity Maxim.

Leech states in his book entitled *Principles of Pragmatics* about the generosity maxim as "speaker has to minimize the expression of beliefs which express or imply benefit to self and maximize the expression of beliefs which express or imply cost to self" (Leech, 1983). The generosity maxim is centered on the speaker and 'others' should be put first instead of the 'self'. It is provided some examples (Leech, 1983) below.

1. You can lend me your car (Impolite)
2. I can lend you my car (Polite)

3. We must come and have dinner with you (Impolite)
4. You must come and have dinner with us (Polite)

The second sentence, which is an offer, and the fourth sentence, which is an invitation, are presumed to be polite for two reasons; the first reason is because they imply benefit to hearer, and the second reason is because they imply cost to self. But in the first and third sentences, the speaker implies benefit to self and cost to other, so those sentences do not belong to generosity maxim.

The factors influencing the application of the generosity maxim in conversation are analyzed by using theory proposed by Holmes (2001). Holmes stated about some factors that can influence the application of politeness, in this case the generosity maxim which is a part of Leech's politeness principles. Holmes also stated about three factors that may influence the application of politeness, such as age, gender, and context of situation.

People's speech varies at different ages (Holmes, 2001). In a conversation between a young participants and an old participants, the languages that the participants used has to be difference with the language they used when they are having a conversation with the people in the same age. This is obviously affected the application of politeness in the conversation. Age may has strong effects in the application of politeness in conversation.

Conversation between people with different gender may also cause the application of politeness in a conversation, especially when they are talking about something precious or privacy. Women and men do not speak in exactly the same way as each other in any community (Holmes, 2001). The way or the feel about how someone speaks to the people with the same gender will be different compared to the way or the feel when he/ she is talking to the people who have different gender.

The last factor described here is the context of situation. People can speak in different ways to each other according to the situation during their conversation. For example, conversation between people in a formal meeting must be having differences compared to the ordinary conversations between friends. Different situation makes different ways for someone to say something to other people. Certain social factors have been relevant for the particular language variety used (Holmes, 2001). These factors are participants (people involved in the conversation), the setting or social context (where they are speaking), the topic (what they are talking about), and the function (the reason why they are speaking).

For the data source, the movie chosen is entitled "Divergent". This movie was released in March 2014 in the United States and directed by Neil Norman Burger, an American film director. This movie lasts for 2 hours and 19 minutes. This movie story focuses on the adventure of a girl called Tris in a futuristic world where the society was divided into some factions or groups based on their natural personalities to keep the peace. This movie is a kind of action movie. This movie is chosen because it is full of tense situation and action scenes, and it seems to be more interesting to observe generosity maxim in this kind of movie rather than in movies describing about everyday modern life or modern teenage stories, which seems like it is very common. Furthermore, this movie is based on an international bestseller novel which has the same title written by an American author Veronica Roth.

2. Method

In analyzing the data of this research, it will be applied a part of Leech's politeness principle theory, that is the theory of generosity maxim (Leech, 1983).

The data in this research is in form of utterances which are spoken by the characters in *Divergent* movie. The utterances which are picked as the data contain the expressions of generosity maxim. It was applied documentation method and note-taking technique in this study.

The first step to start the research is by watching the whole movie. This is done to know and understand the whole story, so it will be easier to analyze the data since the analysis also focuses on the situation when the movie characters utter such utterances. Then the utterances containing the expressions of the generosity maxim will be chosen as data and then noted. To avoid any mistakes, the *Divergent* movie script was downloaded and read as well to compare and check the true utterances spoken by the characters. The utterances noted obviously have to be relevant with the theory applied in analyzing the data in this research. They have to contain the application of the generosity maxim stated by Leech.

After the data had been collected, they were analyzed and the presented in descriptive method. Firstly, the data are showed in form of conversations, and the expressions containing the application of the generosity maxim are presented in bold type. Then, each conversation is followed by the description of the analysis. It is described about how the data is classified into the generosity maxim and what factors caused the application of the generosity maxim in that situation. It is also described a little bit about the situation or what was happening when the movie characters were having the conversation containing the application of the generosity maxim. The data in this research are only limited to the conversation or dialogues in the movie, so any monologues would not be classified as the data of this research.

3. Results and Discussion

The result shows that there are some utterances spoken by the characters of "Divergent" movie contain the application of the generosity maxim. In this part, it is explained about the reason why those utterances are categorized as the generosity maxim and the factor which influences the application of the maxim in the conversation. The data will be presented one by one in form of conversation followed by the analysis. As it is stated before, the data or the expressions containing the maxim were presented in bold type.

(1) In the Corridor of Dauntless Building

[Jeanine stops as she recognizes Tris]

Jeanine : Prior. You're Andrew Prior's daughter, aren't you? Beatrice.

Tris : It's just Tris now.

Jeanine : Tris, I like that.

[Jeanine notices Tris's tattoo just above her chest]

Jeanine : You made an impressive choice, Tris, despite your parents and your test results.

Tris : You've seen my test result?

Jeanine : Of course. I'm glad you were smart enough to know your own mind.
Let me know if you ever need anything.

Data in conversation (1) above is proper to generosity maxim. The conversation was between Tris and Jeanine when they were in corridor of Dauntless building. Tris and her friends were walking down the corridor when they saw Jeanine talking with some people. As Jeanine saw and recognized Tris, she stopped. They had met once before at a big ceremony. Jeanine remembered Tris and her family, the Prior family. "Tris" is a nickname from her real name "Beatrice". She changed her nickname since she left her family and joined with a new faction that she chose.

In generosity maxim, speaker has to minimize the expression of beliefs which express or imply benefit to self and maximize the expression of beliefs which express or imply cost to self (Leech, 1983). In this conversation, Jeanine applied the Generosity Maxim well. Jeanine maximized cost to herself by offering some help to Tris. She got cost more than benefit. Jeanine offered some help to Tris by saying "Let me know if you ever need anything". Jeanine showed her attention to Tris.

The factor which influenced the politeness maxim in the conversation was *context of situation (the function)*. Jeanine as a faction leader spoke politely to Tris, who was just an ordinary faction member. Related to her position as a leader, Jeanine should talk politely to all people so that they would respect her. Thus, Jeanine said something like "let me know if you ever need anything" to show politeness and kindness to Tris and also to make and maintain good relationship between other people and herself. Although the relation between Jeanine and Tris was not close, Jeanine tried to speak politely to Tris by stating that she would help Tris if Tris needed anything.

(2) Four's Room

[Four finishes tending to her wounds and stands]

Four : You should lie down, get some sleep.

Tris : Yeah.

Four : **I'll take the floor.**

[the next morning Tris wakes up to find Four not in the room, as she gets up, Four enters the room]

Four : How are you feeling?

Tris : Better.

Data in conversation (2) is proper to the generosity maxim. The setting of the conversation was in Four's room. Four saved Tris after some people hurt her by trying to throw her into chasm inside Dauntless building, and one of the doers was Tris's friend named Al. After Four defeated those people, he took Tris into his room, gave her a sweater, and took care of her wounds. Since it was already night, Four asked Tris to sleep on the bed in his room, meanwhile Four would sleep on the floor. It can be concluded that Four showed his attention to Tris.

Four said "I'll take the floor". This utterance is belonged to the Generosity Maxim, since Four maximized cost to himself by saying that he would sleep on the floor, and he minimized benefit to himself by letting Tris slept on his bed.

This maxim application was obviously influenced by *gender* factor. As a boy, Four spoke to Tris kindly by showing his attention, especially since Tris's condition was not good as well. Four offered that he would sleep on the floor and let Tris slept on his bed by saying "I'll take the floor". Four showed his generosity to a girl. He let Tris sleep on his bed, while he would sleep on the floor. This also means that Four showed respect to Tris in sharing his bedroom to her.

(3) In Dauntless Building, Near the Chasm

Tris : It's my fault that he's dead.

Four : No, it's not because of you. He made his own choice. He would have been factionless, he was not gonna pass the final test.

Tris : Neither am I.

Four : Why do you say that?

Tris : You know why. And as soon as all the others find out, they're gonna kill me.

Four : **I'm not gonna let that happen.**

Data in conversation (3) can be classified to the generosity maxim. This conversation occurred between Four and Tris after Tris found that her friend named Al died because he committed suicide. Some people found Al's corpse and pull it up from the bottom of chasm, Tris was shocked. After that she remembered the result from her aptitude test long time ago that she was a Divergent. Divergents were people with special personality and way of thinking. The society thought Divergents as threat to the peace. They would be hunted and killed. Tris was really afraid if people found out about this fact. Four had figured it out since Four became her test administrator several times. He realized after seeing Tris' reaction in the test that her true test result was not the same as what she said to everyone. Four wanted to help Tris and did not want her to be in danger.

Four showed his attention to Tris and offered a protection indirectly by saying "I'm not gonna let that happen". Four maximized the cost to himself by protecting Tris, or in other words, by letting himself to be in danger for Tris' sake, and minimized cost to Tris since he would help Tris out. Four minimized benefit to himself as well.

This application of generosity maxim was influenced by *context of situation (the topic)*. The topic of their conversation was the consequences of being Divergents. Four wanted to help and he offered a protection to Tris. Four did not want other people found out the truth. Four said "I'm not gonna let that happen" and it showed that Four did not wanted Tris to be in such a danger. If Tris wanted to survive, the fact that she was a Divergent must be hidden from the people in the society, since they considered Divergent as a trouble for the existence of the faction system in the society, as well as the peace.

(4) Erudite Building – Jeanine's Office

Jeanine: You're aware that Abnegation is undermining the faction system, they're breaking laws, harboring Divergents?

Tris : No, I didn't know that. But if that's true, then I'm glad that I left.

Jeanine: See I need to know that I can count on you to enforce the law, even if it's been broken by someone close to you, someone you care about.

Tris : Of course.

Jeanine: Good. **Then I'll have my car take you back to Dauntless.**

Data in conversation (4) is proper to Generosity Maxim. The conversation was between Jeanine and Tris. At that time, Tris visited her brother, Caleb, in Erudite building. After that, a problem was happened between Tris and two Erudite official. Tris attacked them when suddenly, Jeanine, the leader of Erudite faction, stopped that conflict and then they had a talk in Jeanine's office. Jeanine seemed to be glad that Tris had come to Erudite building and they could talk. When Tris wanted to go back to Dauntless building, Jeanine let Tris to use her car to go back to Dauntless building.

Jeanine applied the generosity maxim by saying "I'll have my car take you back to Dauntless". Jeanine maximized the cost and minimized the benefit to herself by lending Tris her car. Jeanine showed that she cared about Tris, even the Dauntless building was not close from the Erudite building.

Context of situation (the participants) is the factor affected the application of the generosity maxim in the conversation above. The relationship between Jeanine and Tris was not close, but Jeanine still showed her attention by speaking politely to Tris. Jeanine said "I'll have my car take you back to Dauntless" to show her generosity as a leader toward Tris who was just a faction member.

(5) Dauntless Building – Simulation Room

[Four takes Tris into the simulation room]

Four : Shut the door.

[Tris closes the door]

Four : You're gonna practice.

Tris : In my fear landscapes.

Four : **No, in mine. We go in together.**

Data in conversation (5) belongs to the generosity maxim. Four took Tris into a simulation room in Dauntless building to tell Tris how to pass the second training stage and what she should do in order not to be found by the people about her status as a Divergent. A simulation test was done in form of hallucination in the mind of the participant, but this time Four let Tris did it in his mind, in his fear landscapes. Entering someone's mind was not good since it was full of privacy information. Because in this case Four offered help to Tris, it was considered that he applied the generosity maxim. He maximized the cost to himself by letting Tris entered his mind, and he also minimized the cost to Tris since he helped Tris by sharing his knowledge and strategies to Tris. He also accompanied Tris to do the simulation test, although this test was usually done alone by the participants, conducted by the administrator.

The politeness maxim was used in conversation (5) because of *context of situation (the participant)*. Four was a Dauntless instructor and Tris was a Dauntless member. Four showed his attention as an instructor toward a member like Tris by offering help. By saying that utterance, Four showed kindness to Tris. The relation between Tris and Four had been getting closer up to this situation.

4. Conclusion

The application of the generosity maxim is exist and found in Divergent movie. The maxim is applied in utterances spoken by the characters of the movie. Generosity maxim is not much applied in the movie. It is found only some utterances containing the maxim.

The factors which influence the application of the generosity maxim in Divergent movie are gender and context of situation. Context of situation gives more influence to the application of the generosity maxim. If the situation changes, the way how people speak to each other changes as well. Gender does not give much influence to the application of the generosity maxim in Divergent movie.

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The importance of developing android-based Indonesian language dictionary for the blind (KABITUNA)

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Abstract – Indonesia is among the ranks of countries with the lowest literacy in the world. Precisely at rank 69 of 76 countries. If calculated the average Indonesian people only read one book per year. One of the reasons for the low literacy of Indonesia is the lack of understanding of Indonesian society with Indonesian vocabulary. Although Indonesian is an educational language which is also the national language and language of Indonesian unity, it can not be denied if Indonesian people do not fully master the Indonesian language. That's what causes the dictionary as a medium for discovering the meaning of words. On the other hand, until now Indonesia is not evenly able to facilitate the dictionary as a means of searching the meaning of words. Many Indonesian dictionaries only specialize for normal people only. Whereas the number of persons with disabilities in Indonesia reached 2.45% of the total population of Indonesia. Then the blind person is 29.63% of the total number of persons with disabilities. It can be concluded that people with visual impairment are the highest in persons with disabilities in Indonesia. Therefore the development of Indonesian dictionary for the blind is considered important in this era. Android is a Linux-based operating system that can be used for smart phones and tablet computers. The selection of Android as the Indonesian dictionary base for the visually impaired on the Android platforms is provided platform open for developers to create applications. In addition to Android also features Talk Back and speech to text that was created specifically for the visually impaired. The feature works as an Android screen reader so that the blind people can enjoy the screen display with sound output. In line with these things Android is considered easier operation and maintenance because it is more practical than conventional dictionary.

Keywords: dictionary, Indonesian language, android, the blind

1. Introduction

Bahasa Indonesia as the national language, has various functions, namely (1) official state language, (2) official introductory language in educational institutions, (3) official languages in national-level communication for the purposes of planning and implementation of development and governance; (4) the official language in the development of culture, the utilization of science, and the utilization of modern technology (Andayani. 2015). *Bahasa Indonesia* as a union language that has been vowed to the oath of youth October 28, 1928. Then politically Indonesian language is defined as the national language in 1945 Constitution. Since then Indonesian language stands in the highest place in this country.

The function of the Indonesian language, the Indonesian language is good and correct not fully understood by the people of Indonesia. According to *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* (online dictionary), the dictionary is a 'reference containing words and phrases usually arranged alphabetically along with a description of eating, usage, or translation'. The dictionary is a book containing words from a language, usually arranged alphabetically, with a description of its meaning, speech, spelling, etc (Chaer, 2007). Dictionary is a reference book containing a list of words or combinations of words with descriptions of various aspects of meaning and their use in the language, usually arranged alphabetically. From these quotations it can be concluded that the dictionary is a reference containing a list of vocabularies and meanings arranged alphabetically (Fatmawati, 2015; Fauziah, 2014; Martin, 2014).

Preparation of dictionaries using lexicographic science. Lexicography is a branch of lexicology. Lexicography is an activity consisting of research, collection, selection, analysis, and explanation of lexical units (words, word elements, and word combinations) owned by one or more languages in the dictionary. According to the National Socioeconomic Survey (SUSENAS) 2012 (in Disability Bulletin 2014: 6), the percentage of Indonesia's population with disability is 2.45% with details: 39.97% of persons with more than one type of limitations, 29.63% , 10.26% limitations in walking or climbing stairs, 7.87% limitations in listening, 6.70% limitations in concentration, 2.83% limitations in self-care, and 2.74% limitations in communicating. From the explanation, people with visual disability (blind) are ranked second most, while the highest rank is disability which has more than one type of limitations.

On the other hand, in the 21st century this information technology has grown very rapidly. Almost all people in this world use technology. No exception disabilities especially the blind people. KrJogja, one of the electronic newspapers of the Special Territory of Yogyakarta on November 17, 2016 reported that Tio, one of the students of the Faculty of Law, Gadjah Mada University is one of the blind people told about the life of a blind person who can not be away from smartphones with the activation of talkback as a text-reading help facility in the smartphone. For Tio the talkback facility is very useful for his lectures. This is the background of the development of KABITUNA or Indonesian Dictionary for the blind android-based with the help of screen readers or talkback which is one of the features available on Android-based smartphones.

2. Method

There are similar previous studies. In research entitled *Developing Applications of High School Biology Dictionary Based Visual Studio with the Mainstay of Classification of Plants in SMA Jepara* produced a high school Biology dictionary by meeting the criteria of eligibility criteria media based on media and material aspects. The developed dictionary can also improve student learning outcomes. Another research has been conducted in the form of thesis entitled *Mobile Braille Touch (MBT): Development of Media Learning Braille Application Based Android for Blind Person in 2016* (Manea, 2012). The research resulted in the product of learning media writing braille letters based on Android that has been tested feasibility and can be published.

This study has similarities and differences with previous research. When compared with Purnomo's research, this research has in common that is equally developed product in the form of dictionary. However, the dictionary developed by Purnomo is a Biology dictionary, while the dictionary developed in this study is an Indonesian dictionary. In addition, Purnomo developed a dictionary developed with a visual studio based, while the dictionary developed in this study developed with android based. When compared with research Kurniawan, this research has in common that is equally developed products for the android-based blind. However, Research Kurniawan in the form of learning media development, while this research is the development of Indonesian language dictionary.

3. Results and Discussion

KABITUNA is a dictionary application of Indonesian language that is dedicated to users who experience limitations in viewing. Of course, this dictionary is a bit different from the existing dictionary. This difference is intended to further facilitate the user, namely blind, in accessing the dictionary. For now, this product already has 2000 entries, or a base word, and every average entry has four derivative words, so the total number of words in this product reaches 10,000 words.

This vocabulary is selected from high school books, both electronic and printed, and the *Republika* newspaper. The books are biology, mathematics, Indonesian, geography, physics, chemistry, civic education, information technology, economics, and history. Lema is chosen from the terms that are considered difficult or the dilemma is perceived as a term in the field, which then searched its meaning through the Big Indonesian Dictionary. Then the data is processed into a database. Meanwhile, KABITUNA offers easy access. the convenience provided by this product such as, the user does not need to type the word to be searched, the user does not need to read the search results, and the dictionary format has been adapted to the ability of the user so that more easily understood.

The main feature offered by KABITUNA is the existence of a voice search model. This is so that users do not have to type what they are looking for. This feature is supported by a google product called speech to text. This speech to text application is capable of converting voice into a post. No doubt, the accuracy of this application is considered very feasible. The second feature that KABITUNA offers is that users do not need to read the search results. The search results will be presented in the form of

votes. This feature is also supported by a google product called talk back. Google talkback is a screen reader application launched by google and is available in every android device.

The last feature that is not less important is the customization of the dictionary format. This feature is closely related to the second feature. This is because the second feature leaves the problem that the researcher then sought to create his third feature. These adjustments include, the addition of the word 'is' after the word, the word 'sample' before the sample sentence, return of the abbreviation to its original form, and intonation adjustment. The addition of 'is' and 'example' is solely because the language instinct of the researcher is better able to understand the search results using the extra 'is' and the examples' than the ones not. The addition of 'is' is placed on each word, either a base word or a derivative. While the 'example' is placed before the sample sentence. The addition of this 'example' is not as much as the 'is' addition.

One of the issues left by google talkback screen reader apps is that it can not read an abbreviation. Let's say 'n' for the noun abbreviation is read / n / or 'yg' for 'read' / yeg /. Of course this becomes an obstacle to understanding the content, on the other hand, instinctively the language, if a word is spoken, the complete form will be more acceptable than the abbreviated form.

The second problem left by google tlakback is that he is too rigid in reading a text. That is, there is no discrimination in reading or misconduct. Researchers then try to solve this problem by manipulating intonation through punctuation. The punctuation marks used to manipulate them are semicolon (;), point (.) And comma (,). KABITUNA has a menu such as, dictionary, tutorial, about, and contacts. The dictionary menu is the main menu in this product and serves to search for words. While the tutorial menu contains how to use the product completely. Presentation of this tutorial in the form of sound, so that directly can be enjoyed by the user. The menu about is the menu that contains what is kabituna in the general overview. Finally, the contact menu contains the people involved in product creation.

4. Conclusion

Considering the number of entries and their derivative words, the ease with which they are offered, the features also facilitate in accessing applications, as well as menus designed in accordance with the ability of users, it is not excessive if the product is said to be feasible as a dictionary product. Based on the above ideas can be obtained summary as follows. First, the development of KABITUNA is done from the planning stage which contains the analysis of user needs and capabilities as well as analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of talkback feature on android. Second, the design of KABITUNA is designed based on the stages of making use case diagrams, architectural design, and materials collection. Third, validation is done by three validators. The material expert's validator assesses the feasibility of the product, the media expert's validator assesses the feasibility of the product, while the practitioner's validator assesses the feasibility of the product. Based on the results of the three validators will be known KABITUNA worth to be implemented.

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The use of modality markers to perform hegemony politeness in using Balinese language: a case study on *Awig-awig*

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Abstract – This research was aimed at expressing motivation to use modality markers in text of traditional village regulation (*awig-awig*). The data was obtained from some major regulations in five regencies and city in Bali province. Sampling was done based on area considering dialectical and sociocultural diversity. Based on theory of pragmatics, it could be concluded that the use of Balinese language modality in text of traditional village regulation was not merely demanded by syntax and grammatical semantics. It can be proven with deletion technic. Up on the modality deletion, it did not change the prime meaning of text, but the sentences were still grammatical instead. The use of modality was motivated with pragmatic needs, i.e. performing hegemony politeness in accordance with the sense of modality as interpersonal rhetoric.

Keywords: *hegemony politeness, awig-awig, desa pakraman, impassive*

1. Introduction

Awig-awig (traditional regulation) is the basic rule guided by every *desa pakraman* (traditional village). *Awig-awig* written in *basa Bali alus singgih* 'very respectful balinese variety'. The use of the Balinese language variety *alus singgih* positions the audiens on a relative higher social status than the speaker. Thus, the use of the Balinese language of *alus singgih* is a manifestation of the speakers' respect for the speakers.

Respect is the implementation of the principle of language politeness, especially the maxim of wisdom and wisdom (Wijana, 1996) The maxim of wisdom suggests that every speaker minimizes the 'loss' to others; otherwise speakers are required to maximize profits for others. The losses and advantages referred to in this maxim are not solely material losses and benefits - physical but include social values. Losses and advantages of social value cannot be measured materially, but rather on the socio-philological aspect. The use of polarized variants may benefit these sociological-psychological aspects.

The other maxim which is in accordance with respect is the maxim of humility. Maxim is centered on the speaker's self. This maxim outlines that each speaker increases his or her own losses. Its implementation in the use of Balinese language is if the speech is intended for itself then used the lower variety of Balinese languages (*andap* and/or *alus sor*). Conversely, if the speech was addressed to speakers or a third person used a variety of high Balinese language (*alus singgih*). The culture of using Balinese language is in line with the ethics of using language which states that “*wasita nimitanta nemu mitra*” and “*wasista nimitanta nemu suka*” i.e. by talking appropriately we can find friends and by talking appropriately we can find happiness (Jendra, 1999). Speaking ethics in Hinduism is very relevant to the principle of language politeness that becomes a pragmatic study. In addition to the ethics of the talk, there is also a concept of social interaction adopted by Balinese society, namely *tatakan raos* meaning 'base of speech'. *Tatakan raos* is to convey a statement accompanied by a description of capital or condition. This is the focus of the study in this article.

2. Method

This research was conducted on Balinese speech constructions used in *awig-awig*. The data was taken from the samples taken by taking into account the Balinese dialectal variants as well as the differentiation of the local culture. With this sampling technique, the sample of this study was determined: (1) in the eastern part of Bali, data was taken from Karangasem regency, i.e. Awig-Awig Menanga and Rendang, 2) in the south Bali area, data was taken from Awig-awig Pakraman village Sumerta, Denpasar; (3) for the area of western Bali, data was taken from Awig-awig Baler Bale Agung, Jembrana, (4) for the northern part of Bali, data was taken from Awig-awig Desa Adat Penarukan dan Alap Sari, Buleleng; and (5) for the area of central Bali, data was taken from Awig-Awig Desa Pakraman Batur Sari, Gianyar. Data was collected by document recording techniques, observation and interviews with a number of informants.

3. Results and Discussion

In syntactic studies, modalities often function as phrases so that they are more popular with capital information. A capital description is used to require something to happen or a proposition that either ignores or denies the possibility or necessity. Modality can also be the way a speaker expressing attitudes toward a situation in an interpersonal communication (Kridalaksana, 1993). In *awig-awig*, modality is often used as a linguistic marker to express language politeness. To support this deduction, we present examples of texts quoted from *awig-awig* of traditional village.

Yen krama madruwe semeton sane sampun maperabian, sowang-sowang patut tedun ngayah kawastanin ayah ngarep (awig-awig Desa Adat Penarukan, paos 12)

'If the residents who have got married, each of them must *ngayah*, called *ayah ngarep*'

The text of section 12 uses *yen* modality 'if' which serves as a description phrase. Syntactically and semantically, the section 12 can be expressed in the following sentence without altering the meaning of the sentence.

Krama sane madruwe semeton sampun maperabian, sowang-sowang patut tedun ngayah kawastanin ayah ngarep.

'Residents who have brothers already married, each must *ngayah*, called *ayah ngarep*'

The removal of modalities in the above modified text does not change the message at all. This lingual fact proves that the use of capital information in the modified sentence is neither syntactic nor semantic; but rather to pragmatic considerations, especially the principle of modesty in language. By many Balinese speakers, the use of the *yen* 'if' modality, such as the original text of the section 12, is perceived as more polite than the modified sentence by omitting its capital statement. Standing on one data is certainly not enough to take a conclusion. Therefore, the following data presents a number of other data related to the use of modalities in regulation of traditional village in Bali.

Prade wenten krama desa megenah ringkarang desa tur magentos agama ring siosan, karang desa inucap pacang kakeninin sewa manut pararem desa/ banjar (paos 45 awig-awig Desa Adat Penarukan).

'If there is a resident residing in the village and converting to another religion, the resident will be charged a rent in accordance with the sub-village regulation concerned'.

Text of section 45 on *awig-awig desa Pakraman Penarukan*, Buleleng uses a partial inversion sentence structure, i.e. adverb of time *prade wenten*, 'n case there is' precedes the subject of a sentence, while the predicate remains in position after the subject. Modality *Prade wenten* is a *tatakan raos* as a representation of the attitude of traditional village institutions to its citizens. When examined, the text of illocutionary in section 45 is a punishment. Customary village institutions will charge a rent to

residents shifting to other religion from Hindu who occupy traditional village land. This sanction is actually a fairly rational consequence, because every Hindu follower who occupies the customary village land is subject to *ayah-ayahan* 'customary and religious obligations'; whereas if someone who occupy the customary village land that follows other religion is directly released from the religious and social obligation and duties. Because it is no longer tied to the obligation and duties 'ayah-ayahan' then the right to use the village land was revoked and replaced with rent. The use of *prade* unwanted 'if any' modalities can foster a sense of inferiority. The Section can be changed by losing its capital, and having the same meaning, but losing its inferiority. Other data are presented to strengthen this analysis.

Yening tan masangah panguluning karang, akakubon kabawos. Tan yogya genah ngraksa sawa. Yening wenten mamurug, yogya katiwakin pamidanda mrayascita palemahan punika (chapter 3 section 28 awig-awig Desa Adat Menanga, Karangasem)

'If a house does not have a family temple at the house compound, it is called *Akakubon*. The house is not allowed to be a place to keep dead body prior funeral or cremation. If they violate the rule they shall be given a sanction, i.e. to purify the compound.

The text of paragraph 3 of section 28 in the Menanga customary *awig-awig* uses twice the *yening* modalities 'if' and always at the beginning of the sentence. This lingual fact further strengthens the analysis that the use of modalities as *tatakan raos*. The text may be constructed differently by discriminating the modalities, for example, as follows.

Akakubon inggih punika sane tan madaging sanggah panguluning karang. Akakubon tan yogya genah ngraksa sawa. Sane mamurug, yogya katiwakin pamidanda mrayascita palemahan punika (verse 3 section 28 awig-awig Desa Adat Menanga, Karangasem)

'*Akakubon* is a house which does not have family temple at the house compound. It is not allowed to be a place to keep the dead body. Those who violate the rule will be given sanction, i.e. to purify the house compound concerned.

The text of this modification has the same meaning as the original text of paragraph 3 of the 28 section. Semantically and syntactically, the modified text does not have any issues. But pragmatically, prioritizing locality, illocutionary and perlocutionary fit, the more relevant option is the original construction, which uses the modalities. The choice of original construction is because there is a value of politeness that is manifested by the use of capital information. Here are some data on modalities used to represent Balinese language politeness.

Yening wenten maubuh-ubuhan sajeroning pekarangan, hugi mratyaksayang pakarang ipun, mangda tan ngawetuang bhaya, taler mangda hapik, urati, siksa mangda tan kantos ngaletihin ngobetin, cerobe karang pomahan wiadin palemahan panyandinge. Yening wenten mamurug tan siksa ring hingon-hingon miwah kandang ipun, wenang panyandinge nyambatsara. Yening akas sang kesambatsara wenang

katengahang ka desa, prajuru desa nepasin. Wenagn katiwakin dandha manut panglokika (v. 6 section 29 awig-awig Desa Adat Menanga, Karangasem).

'If there is (a) raising livestock in the yard of the house, they must pay attention to the compound so that it does not reveal danger, they have to be careful, diligent, so that it does not cause any pollution, disturb the compound as well as their neighboring houses. If there is a violation, no attention, caring for it, neighbors can remind. If it is still ignored, it can be reported to the village, village officials straighten. They will be fined in accordance with the rule'

Prade wenten taru sane mentik ring sajeroning wates kengin kawara panyading, mangda taru inucap karebah kasaksinin antuk prajuru desa tur taru inucap kapinaro tiga, asiki katur ring prajuru sane maritetes, muah sane kakalih kaepah sang madruwe wates manut lokika (ayat 2 pasal 30, awig-awig desa adat Rendang, Karangasem).

'If there is a tree growing at the border and the neighbors object, the tree shall be cut down in the presence of the village administrator and the tree is divided into three, one part for the village administrator, and the other two parts are for those living in the borders based on the rule'

Prade tamiune pacang madunungan jantos awuku ring awuku, I kelihan patut nureksain, pisan mungguing maka buatannya miwah surat-surat keterangannya (verse 2 section 46 awig-awig Desa Adat Sumerta, Denpasar)

'If the guest will stay overnight for more than one week, the village chairman shall check, ask for his purpose, his recommendation letter'

Prade pidaging paruman nenten kaingkupin, mangda prajuru desa ngilikang babawos, saha pamutusnya kasobyahang mangda kararemin olih krama desa, bilih tan prasida kasungkemin jantos ping tiga, prajuru desa wenang nunas bawos ring sang ngawewenang (ayat 3 paos 20 awig-awig desa adat Batur Sari, Gianyar).

'If the contents of the meeting are not agreed, the village officials shall moderate the decision, and the decision is socialized in order to be agreed upon by the citizens, if also not approved up to three times, village administrators may ask the authorities'

Prade wenten kalayusekaran rikala wenten piodalan, dados mendem sasiliban, tan pasadok tur mamargi ri wengi ka setra (verse 4 section 43 awig-awig Desa Adat Batur Sari, Gianyar).

'If there is a death at a religious ceremony, it can be buried in a hidden way, not reporting and leaving for the grave at night'

Yening salih sinunggil wenten ngelengit (nakal) ten polih pekraman (pasal 13 section 19 awig-awig banjar pakraman Beler Bale Agung, Jembrana)

'In case of anyone cheats, he or she will be removed from the village'

Yening wenten salah sinunggil warga krama nenten mabersih nyabrang rahina purnama–tilem, olih prajuru mangda kaicen pawarah-warrah tur wewanengan 3 (tigang) rahina, taler nenten kalaksanayang pacang kasanggra olih krama banjar (kerojog), wenang kakenin danda akwehnyane Rp 10.000,00 (ayat 16 paos 19 awig-awig banjar pakraman Baler Bale Agung)

'If any one of the residents does not take a part in mutual assistance such as cleaning the compound on every full moon and dark month, the village committee shall give a warning and within 3 (three) days, if it is still ignored, he/she will be picked up by the sub-village members shall be fined Rp 10.000,00'

All the above data quotes taken from various *awig-awig* sources, place the modalities as *tatakan raos* to build hegemonic politeness among indigenous peoples.

Based on existing data, it is known that the use of modalities is to declare certainty in the future. This means that if the conditions occur, then the consequences also must occur; on the contrary if the requirements are not met then the consequences would not happen. The act of speech acts to assert certainty is called commissive. It is insisted that verbs of speech acts included in commissive illocution is 'promise' and 'offer' (Austin, 1975). Based on existing data on regulation of traditional village (*awig-awig desa adat / banjar pakraman*) throughout Bali, it was revealed that verbs required were included in commissure illusions. The use of word verbs requires ensuring certainty will occur in the future if the modalities are met. Conversely, if the modalities are not met, as the result it does not certainly occur. Thus, the verbs of the word act require to be included in commissive illocutionary acts.

The use of modalities is not merely the demands of syntax and grammatical semantics, but is a pragmatic one, especially the implementation of the principle of decency. It is said that it is not syntactic and semantic condition because it is proven after the original text that uses the modality is reconstructed by eliminating its modalities, it does not change the subject of grammatical semantics. Rearranging the text by devouring its modalities also retains its syntactic structure. Thus, the use of modalities is not demotivated by grammatical and semantic needs, but is motivated by interpersonal conditions.

Modality is a rhetorical proposition for building and maintaining social relationships. This is in line with the concept of *tri hita karana* in Hindu philosophy; which one of its elements maintain human relationships with humans (*pawongan*). The use of the modalities marker is motivated by the need to maintain common harmony. The use of the modal modifier places the speaker in an honorable position. Thus, the use of the modality marker is a linguistic instrument for building hegemonic politeness.

4. Conclusion

At the end of this scientific study, the principal conclusion is drawn that the use of modalities in the *pakraman* village *awig-awig* is not a grammatical syntactic and semantic targets, but rather a pragmatic demand for internal compliance. Internal

people's obedience is what I call hegemonic politeness. Thus, the use of the capitalist marker is a linguistic instrument for the cultivation of hegemonic politeness to indigenous peoples in Bali.

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Phonological variation of Javanese in Kebumen district

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Abstract – Geographically, Kebumen regency is a border area of Javanese dialect Banyumas (*ngapak*) and Yogyakarta dialect (*bandhek*). Language speakers in this region have their own language phenomenon. The purpose of this research is to describe phonological variation of Javanese language in Kebumen district. These variations include vowel sounds and consonant sounds, as well as other sound variations. To obtain the necessary data, the researcher used interview, record, and introspection techniques. Interviews were based on a gloss list provided to speakers of the language. The researchers recorded the interview. In addition, researchers also directly record the process of speaking of the speakers directly. The technique of introspections was done because researchers are speakers of language in Kebumen district. The analysis was done by comparing the Java language in Kebumen district with the standard Java language. The results obtained from this study showed that based on the residence, speakers and the social groups of Javanese speakers in Kebumen District have variations of vowel phoneme / a /, / i /, / u /, / e /, / o /, and consonant / b /, / d /, / k /, / g /, as well as variations of sound [r], [h], [-əw-], and [-ək]. The result of variation obtained is phoneme / a / pronounced [a], [ɔ], [ə], and [ɛ]. The phoneme / i / is pronounced [i], [I], and [ɛ]. The phoneme / u / is pronounced [u], and [U]. The phoneme / e / is pronounced [e] and [ɛ]. The phoneme / o / is pronounced [o] and [ɔ]. For the phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, and / k / pronounced fixed as [b], [d], [g], and [k] which in standard Java is pronounced [p], [t], [k], and [ʔ]. The phoneme / r / can be inserted in the word. Phoneme / h / uninstalled. In addition, the sounds [-əw-] and [-ək] respectively as variants of the [-uw-] and [-aʔ] sounds.

Keywords: *variation, phoneme, Javanese language, Kebumen*

1. Introduction

Geographically, Kebumen regency is a border area of Javanese dialect of Banyumas (*ngapak*) and dialect of Yogyakarta (*bandhek*), thus speakers of language in this region have their own language phenomenon. During this time, the assumption that the boundary of dialect between Banyumas and Yogyakarta is in Prembun area which is bounded by a Gebang river flowing from north to south which precisely as limiting Kebumen Regency and Purworejo Regency or as barrier of language area *ngapak* and *bandhek*. However, the phenomenon of Javanese variation occurs in Kebumen district is really unique. Kebumen Regency has 26 districts (1) Ayah, (2) Buayan, (3) Rowokele, (4) Kuwarasan, (5) Gombong, (6) Sempor, (7) Puring, (8) Adimulyo, (9) Karanganyar, (10) Karanggayam, (11) Pejagoan, (12) Petanahan, (13) Klirong, (14) Sruweng, (15), Bulus Pesantren, (16) Ambal, (17) Kebumen, (18) Kutowinangun, (19) Mirit, (20) Prembun, (21) Sadang, (22) Alian, (23) Poncowarno, (24) Karang Sambung, (25) Padureso, and (26) Bonorowo.

The purpose of this research is to describe phonological variation of Java language in Kebumen District (BJKK). Phonological variation is a variation that occurs due to changes in phoneme sound, either vowel or consonant phonemes, influenced by internal or external factors. Phoneme is a smallest unit of sound that can distinguish the meaning of the word (Chaer, 2009). From this definition, it is clear that phonemes are sounds of language that can distinguish meaning, in other words if it does not distinguish meaning, it will not be a phoneme. Phoneme is also the smallest unit of sound that is able to show contrast meaning (Kridalaksana, 2001).

Language variation can be divided into two types, namely internal variation and external variation (Nababan, 1984). Internal variation is a variation caused by factors that exist in the language itself, such as phonological variation, a phoneme as a result of the influence of other phonemes that precede or follow it which is a natural feature of a language, external variation is a variation caused by outside factors language, such as the speaker's home area, the social class of the speaker, the topic of speech, the atmosphere of speech, and others. These variations include vowel sounds and consonant sounds, as well as other sound variation.

2. Method

There are seven Points of Research (TP) which is used as data collection point. The reason for choosing these seven TPs is because the TP has a phenomenon of a noticeable variation of sound compared to other areas. The seven places are presented in the table below.

Table 1 Number of TP, Villaage and TP District

Number of TP	Village Name	TP District.
1	Kebumen	Kebumen
2	Sumberjati	Ambal
3	Kutowinangun	Kutowinangun
4	Kertodeso	Mirit

5	Tlogodepok	Mirit
6	Prembun	Prembun
7	Padureso	Padureso

To obtain the necessary data, the researcher uses interview, record, and introspection techniques. Interviews are based on a gloss list provided to speakers of the language. The researchers recorded the interview. In addition, researchers also directly record the process of speaking speakers directly. The technique of introspection is done because researchers are speakers of language in Kebumen district. While the analysis is done by means of Javanese language comparison in Kebumen district with Standard Java Language (BJB).

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the data obtained from the seven TPs, it can be seen that BJKK have similarities and differences with the BJB. Among the differences described here include the phonological variation. In addition, in BJKK alone the phonological variation between TPs and TPs also has similarities and differences. For more details BJKK description described as follows.

Phonological Variation of BJKK

Based on the phonological mapping that has been made, it can be seen that BJKK has several phonological variations. Phonological variation is a variation in the use of phonetic sound and does not distinguish meaning. Variations are formed because of the location of different native speakers and groups of speakers.

Phonological variation in the use of BJKK also cannot be separated from the above factors. The variations based on the location of different regions include variations of the phoneme / a /, / i /, / u /, / e /, / o /, / b /, / d /, / g /, / k / and the variation of the sound [r], [h], [-əw-], [-ək-], and [a?]. The example variations are as follows.

3.1 Variation of phoneme / a /

(1) / a / pronounced [a] in TP1

Example: / flower / - [flower] 'go' (242)

/ what / - [what] 'what' (14)

/ five / - [five] 'five' (170)

The phoneme / a / is pronounced [a] by all groups of speakers in TP 1, ie a group of highly educated speakers, both old and young, and a group of highly educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with TP 1 are located in most areas of Kebumen District, including the subdistrict: (1) Father, (2) Buayan, (3) Rowokele, (4) Kuwarasan, (5) Gombong, (6) Sempor (7) Puring, (8) Adimulyo, (9) Karanganyar, (10) Karanggayam, (11) Pejagoan, (12) Petanahan, (13) Klirong, (14) Sruweng, (15) Bulus Pesantren, (16) Kebumen, (17) Prembun (northern part), (18) Sadang, (19) Alian, (20) Poncowarno), and (21) Karang Sambung.

When compared to the BJB, the // interest /, / what /, and / five / words of this TP are pronounced [luŋɔ], [ɔpɔ], and [limɔ] in BJB. This indicates that BJKK in TP 1 is a dialect different from BJB. The phonem / a / pronunciation is included in the BJ dialect of Banyumas.

(2) / a / pronounced [a], [ɔ], [ɛ], [ə] in TP 2

Example: / flower / - [luŋa], [luŋɔ], [luŋɛ], [luŋə] 'go' (242)

/ what / - [what], [ɔpɔ], [apɛ], [apə], 'what' (14)

/ five / - [five], [limɔ], [lime], [limə] 'five' (170)

Phonem / a / pronounced [a], [ɔ], [ɛ], [ə] by speakers in TP 2, ie highly educated speakers, both old and low and low-educated speakers, both aged or young. The areas that have similarities with TP 2 include the area of Ambal sub-district, especially the villages through which the south-south alternative route is Daendeles and located south of the Luwangan River, among them Sumberjati Village, Kaibon, Ambarresmi, Ambal, Blengorkulon, Blengorwetan, Benerwetan, Benerkulon, Ambalkliwonan, Pasarsenen, Ambalberek, Pucangan, Kenojayan, Kembaran, and Entak.

This TP has four variations of phoneme pronunciation / a /. This indicates that this TP is a dialect transition. In addition to having elements of Banyumas dialect, also get the influence of BJB, namely the entry of the earth [ɔ]. It also has its own characteristics, namely the pronunciation of phonemes / a / being / ɛ / and / ə /. The use of such variations is characteristic of this area, so that when the speakers speak it will sound strange to speakers of other regions. Because it is considered to have a language disorder, speakers from other regions call it the term Ceblek Java language.

(3) / a / pronounced [ɔ] in TP 3,4,5,6

Example: / flower / - [lungɔ] 'go' (242)

/ what / - [ɔpɔ] 'what' (14)

/ five / - [limɔ] 'five' (170)

This variation occurs in four TP 3,4,5,6 and is spoken by all highly educated speakers, both old and young and low educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with this TP include Kutowinangun Village, villages throughout Mirit Sub-district, villages in Bonorowo Subdistrict, and parts of Kedungwaru, Tunggalroso, Kembipaten Sembir, and Kedungbulus. The phoneme pronunciation indicates that in this TP it has gained influence from BJB. It is because this area is traversed by provincial road.

(4) / a / pronounced [a], [ɔ] in TP 7

Example: / flower / - [flower], [lungɔ] 'go' (242)

/ what / - [what], [ɔpɔ] 'what' (14)

/ five / - [five], [limɔ] 'five' (170)

This variation only occurs in TP 7. This variation is used by all groups of speakers. Either groups of highly educated, elderly or younger speakers, or groups of low educated speakers of both old and young. The areas that have similarities in TP 7 that includes all villages in District Padureso and some northern Prembun District

such as Mulyosri village, Kabuaran, Pesuningan, and Pecarikan. Geographically this area lies in the border area.

Such variation indicates that in the TP it is also a transitional dialect region, but retention is still strong and has little BJB effect. Its effect is the entry of the sound [ɔ]. Such circumstances are caused by the geographical location of the TP in the mountainous area and away from the city (main highway).

3.2 Variation of phoneme / i /

Variations of phoneme / i / become [i], [I], [ɛ] occur in closed syllable ultima position. The variation of the variation is described as an example below:

(1) / i / is pronounced [i] in TP 1,7

Example: / getih / - [gum] 'blood' (74)

/ gajih / - [gajih] 'fat' (167)

/ white / - [white] 'white' (248)

The phoneme / i / is pronounced [i] by all groups of speakers in TP 1 and TP 7, ie a group of highly educated speakers, both old and young, and a group of low-educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with this TP are located in most areas of Kebumen Regency, including the subdistrict: (1) Father, (2) Buayan, (3) Rowokele, (4) Kuwarasan, (5) Gombong, (6) Sempor (7) Puring, (8) Adimulyo, (9) Karanganyar, (10) Karanggayam, (11) Pejagoan, (12) Land, (13) Klirong, (14) Sruweng, (15) Bulus Pesantren, (16) Kebumen, (17) Prembun (northern part), (18) Sadang, (19) Alian, (20) Poncowarno), (21) Karang Sambung, and (22) Padureso.

When compared to BJB, the words [gajih], [getih], and [white] on TP 1, are pronounced [gajIh], [getIh], and [putIh] in BJB. This indicates that BJKK in TP 1 and TP 7 are different dialects with BJB. The phoneme pronunciation is BJ dialect Banyumas.

(2) / i / is pronounced [I] in TP 3,4,5,6

Example: / getih / - [getIh] 'blood' (74)

/ gajih / - [gajIh] 'fat' (167)

/ white / - [putIh] 'white' (248)

This variation occurs in four TP TP 3,4,5,6 and is spoken by all highly educated speakers, both old and young and low educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with the TP include Kutowinangun Village, villages throughout Mirit Sub-district, villages in Bonorowo Subdistrict, and some villages in Prembun Sub-district, such as Prembun Village, Kabekelan, Bagung, Kedungwaru, Tunggalroso, Kembipaten Sembir, and Kedungbulus.

The phoneme pronunciation indicates that in this TP it has been influenced by BJB.

(3) / i / is pronounced [i], [I], [ɛ] in TP 2

Example: / getih / - [getih], [getIh], [getɛh] 'blood' (74)

/ gajih / - [laj], [gajIh], [gajɛh] 'fat' (167)

/ white / - [white], [putIh], [putɛh] 'white' (248)

The phoneme / i / is pronounced [i], [I], and [ɛ]. Among the phoneme pronunciation there are differences. The pronunciations / i / as [I] and [ɛ] are used by

all groups of speakers in TP 2, i.e. groups of highly educated speakers, both old and young and low-educated group speakers, both old and young. While the phoneme pronunciation / i / as / ε / is only used by groups of speakers who are high educated and low aged. The use of [ε] by the group of speakers aims for prestige, so that they are regarded as persons of high social standing. The areas that have similarities with the TP 2 covering part of the Ambal District, especially the villages through which the south-south alternative route or the Daendeles Road and located south of the Luwangan River are Sumberjati Village, Kaibon, Ambarresmi, Ambal, Blengorkulon, Blengorwetan, Benerwetan, Benerkulon, Ambalkliwonan, Pasarsenen, Ambalberek, Pucangan, Kenojayan, Kembaran, and Entak.

By having three variations of the phoneme / i /. This indicates that this TP is a dialect transition. In addition to having elements of Banyumas dialect, i.e. [i], also get the influence of BJB, i.e. the entry of sounds [I] and [ε].

3.3 Variation of phoneme / u /

Variations of phoneme / u / being [u], and [U] occur in the closed syllable syllables position. Differences variation is described as an example below:

(1) / u / pronounced [u] in TP 1,7

Example: / bales / - [bales] 'bones' (297)

/ steam / - [steam] 'smoke' (15)

/ watuk / - [watuk] 'cough' (30)

The phoneme / u / is pronounced [u] by all groups of speakers in TP 1 and TP 7, ie a highly educated group, both old and young, and a group of low-educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with the TP are located in most areas of Kebumen District, including the sub-district of (1) Ayah, (2) Buayan, (3) Rowokele, (4) Kuwarasan, (5) Gombong, (6) Sempor (7) Puring, (8) Adimulyo, (9) Karanganyar, (10) Karanggayam, (11) Pejagoan, (12) Petanahan, (13) Klirong, (14) Sruweng, (15) Bulus Pesantren, (16) Kebumen, (17) Prembun (northern part), (18) Sadang, (19) Alian, (20) Poncowarno, (21) Karang Sambung, and (22) Padureso.

When compared to BJB, the words [balung], [steamed], and [watuk] on TP 1 and TP 7 are pronounced [balUng], [kukUs], and [watUk] in BJB. This indicates that BJKK in TP 1 and TP 7 are different dialects of BJB. The phoneme pronunciation / u / as [u] is BJ dialect Banyumas.

(2) / u / pronounced [U] in TP 3,4,5,6

Example: / baling / - [balung] 'bone' (297)

/ steam / - [kukUs] 'smoke' (15)

/ watuk / - [watUk] 'cough' (30)

This variation occurs in four TP TP 3,4,5,6 and is spoken by all highly educated speakers, both old and young and low educated speakers, both old and young. The areas that have similarities with the TP include Kutowinangun Village, villages throughout Mirit Sub-district, villages in Bonorowo Subdistrict, and some villages in Prembun Sub-district, such as Prembun Village, Kabekelan, Bagung, Kedungwaru, Tunggalroso, Kembipaten Sembir, and Kedungbulus.

The phoneme pronunciation indicates that in this TP it has gained influence from BJB.

(3) / u / pronounced [u] and [U] in TP 2

Example: / balung / - [balung] and [balUng] 'bone' (297)

/ steamed / - [steamed] and [kukUs] 'smoke' (15)

/ watuk / - [watuk] and [watUk] 'cough' (30)

The phoneme / u / pronounced [u], and [U] .The variation is spoken by all groups of speakers, ie groups of highly educated speakers, both old and young and low-educated speakers, both old and young. . The areas that have similarities with the TP 2 covering part of the Ambal District, especially the villages through which the south-south alternative route or the Daendeles Road and located south of the Luwangan River are Sumberjati Village, Kaibon, Ambarresmi, Ambal, Blengorkulon, Blengorwetan, Benerwetan, Benerkulon, Ambalkliwonan, Pasarsenen, Ambalberek, Pucangan, Kenojayan, Kembaran, and Entak.

Such phoneme variation indicates that this TP is a transitional dialect region. In addition to having elements of the Banyumas dialect, i.e. [i], also gets the influence of BJB, i.e. the inclusion of sound [I].

3.4 Variation of phoneme / e /

The phoneme / e / may vary into [e], [ɛ]. Differences variation is described as an example below:

(1) / e / pronounced [ɛ] in TP 1

Example: / esuk / - [ɛsuk] 'am' (234)

/ bledheg / - [blɛDɛg] 'thunder' (99)

/ ngumbe / - [ngumbɛ] 'to drink' (222)

/ kelek / - [kɛlɛk] 'armpit' (147)

/ afternoon / - [sɔrɛ] 'afternoon' (273)

All groups of speakers of TP 1 always say the phoneme / e / as [e] at the ultima or penultima position, both open and closed syllables. This is so different from the one in the BJB, ie just saying [e] in the closed syllable syllables position.

(2) / e / pronounced [e] in TP 2,3,4,5,6,7

Example: / esuk / - [esUk] 'morning' (234)

/ bledheg / - [blɛDɛg] 'thunder' (99)

/ ngumbe / - [ngumbe] 'to drink' (222)

/ kelek / - [kelek] 'armpit' (147)

/ afternoon / - [afternoon] 'afternoon' (273)

Variations of this sound occur in the ultimate or penultimate like or open position. Whereas in closed to, the phoneme / e / is pronounced as [ɛ]. For words that contain the sound [ɛ] on the ultimate syllable, the penultimate syllable, if it is phoneme / e / adjusts to sound [ɛ] .

This sound variation is used by all groups of speakers from all TPs, except TP 1 and is spoken by all groups of speakers, both high and low educated and young and old.

3.5 Variation of phoneme / o /

Variations of phoneme / o / become [ɔ], [o] can occur in the ultimate position as well as the penultimate of open syllables and closed syllables. Differences variation is described as an example below:

(1) / o / pronounced [ɔ] in TP 1

Example: / kulon / - [kulɔn] 'west' (25)

/ kowe / - [kɔwe] 'thou' (93)

This variation of sound always occurs in TP 1. All groups of speakers use this variation, either high or low educated or old and young. Both the position of the ultimate and the penultimate of open syllables and closed syllables are always pronounced as [ɔ]. However there is some limited number of data in phoneme / o / fixed [o], for example:

/ goblog / - [gɔblog] 'stupid' (59)

/ bodho / - [bɔDo] 'stupid' (59)

/ wolu / - [Wɔlu] 'eight' (80)

(2) / o / pronounced [o] in TP 2 and 7

Example: / afternoon / - [afternoon], 'afternoon' (273)

/ kowe / - [kɔwe], 'thou' (93)

This variation shows that this TP is a meeting area, so it has more variation. This variation is used by all groups of speakers.

(3) / o / pronounced [o] and [ɔ] in TP 3,4,5, and 6

Example: / afternoon / - [afternoon], [sɔre] 'afternoon' (273)

/ kowe / - [kɔwe], [kɔwe] 'thou' (93)

Variations of sound like this occur in the penultimate syllable position open. This variation is spoken by a group of highly educated speakers of old and young, and lowly educated young people. As for the group of low-educated old speakers pronounce / o / as [ɔ] in that position.

It suggests that a group of low-educated speakers of old age still retains BJ dialect Banyumas, while other groups of speakers have been influenced by BJB.

3.6 Variation of phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, / k /

This variation is seen when compared to the phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, / k / in BJB in terms of pronunciation. In BJKK the phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, / k / is pronounced as sounds [b], [d], [g], and [k] by all groups of speakers in all TPs. Unlike the BJB that pronounces phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, / k / as [p], [t], [k], and [?].

3.7 Variation of sound [r]

Variations of sound [r] are present in TP 2 only.

Example: [sandals] - [srandal] 'footwear' (6)

[ragil] - [wragil] 'youngest child' (12)

Speakers who use this variation are low-educated speakers of old or young.

3.8 Variation of sound [h]

Variations of sound [h] may be the removal or addition of phonemes / h /, depending on which TP is referenced. For example is the word 'cause' (340) / maraih

/, in TP 1 spoken [maraih] by all groups of speakers. While in other TP is pronounced [marai]. Another example is 'blood' (74) / getih /, in TP 1 pronounced [gətih], in other TP spoken [gətIh], but in TP 4 groups of low-educated and elderly speakers say [getI]. Other words ending in phoneme / h / in pronunciation are also abandoned. The sound variation corresponds but does not distinguish the meaning.

3.9 Variations of sound [-əw-] and [-uw-]

Examples of sound variations [-əw-] and [-uw-] are as follows:

[ləwih] - [luwIh] 'more' (339)

[kləwih] - [kluwIh] 'a kind of jackfruit' (303)

Variations of sound like this occur throughout the TP. Variations of sound [-əw-] are spoken by a group of low educated speakers of old and young and variations [-uw-] are spoken by a group of highly educated young and old-age speakers. It appears that groups of speakers who use the variation of sound [-əw-] are still influenced by the Banyumas dialect, whereas groups of speakers who use the [-uw-] sound variation have been influenced by the Yogyakarta dialect which is the standard of the Javanese language and taught through the schools.

3.10 Variation of sound [-ək] and [-aʔ]

Examples of the [-ək] and [-aʔ] Sound variations are as follows:

[cəcək] - [cəcaʔ] 'lizard' (68)

Variation of sound [-ək] is spoken by all groups of BJKK speakers. The sound [-ək] in BJKK corresponds to the sound of [-aʔ] In the BJB, so that the word / cecek / 'lizard' is pronounced [cəcək] in BJKK and pronounced [cəcaʔ] In BJB. The [-ək] sound is one of BJ's distinctive dialect of Banyumas and the [-aʔ] Sound is characteristic of BJB.

3.11 Variation of sounds [a] and [ə]

Examples of sound variations [a] and [ə] are as follows:

[jawah] - [jawəh] 'rain'

[gamers] - [gadəh] 'has'

[Dawah] - [Dawəh] 'falling'

Variations of sound like this occur throughout the TP. Variations of sounds [-a-] are spoken by a group of highly educated speakers of old and young and variation [-ə-] are spoken by a group of low educated young and old age. It seems that groups of speakers who use the variation of sound [-ə-] are still influenced by the Banyumas dialect, whereas groups of speakers using sound variations [-a-] have been influenced by the Yogyakarta dialect used as the standard of the Javanese language and taught through the schools.

Based on the above description it can be concluded that BJKK has six vowel phonemes, ie / a /, / i /, / u /, / e /, / o /, and / ə /. The difference with BJB is in the pronunciation of the phoneme. For more details note the following table:

Table 3. Distribution of BJKK Vocal Phonemes

Vocal FONEM TP 1 TP 2 TP Other BJB Vocals

/ a / [a] [a], [ɔ], [ə], [ɛ] [a], [ɔ] [a], [ɔ]
/ i / [i] [i], [I], [ɛ] [i], [I] [i], [I]
/ u / [u] [u], [U] [u], [U] [u], [U]
/ e / [ɛ] [ɛ], [ə] [ɛ], [ə] [ɛ], [ə]
/ o / [ɔ] [o], [ɔ] [o], [ɔ] [o], [ɔ]
/ e / [ə] [ə] [ə] [ə]

From the table above it can be seen that there are three groups of different vowel phonemes. The first group is the TP 1. The speakers of BJKK in TP 1 pronounce the phoneme / a / as [a], phoneme / i / as [i], phoneme / u / as [u], phoneme / e / as [ɛ], phoneme / o / as [ɔ], and the phoneme / e / as [ə]. The second group is in TP 2. The speakers of BJKK in TP 2 pronounce the phoneme / a / as [a], [ɔ], [ə], and [ɛ], phoneme / i / as [i], [I], and [ɛ], phoneme / u / as [u] and [U], phoneme / e / as [ɛ] and [e], phoneme / o / as [ɔ] and [o], and phonem / e / as [ə]. The third group is TP 3,4,5,6, and 7. The BJKK speakers in the TP pronounce phonem / a / as [a] and [ɔ], phoneme / i / as [i] and [I], phoneme / u / as [u] and [U], phoneme / e / as [ɛ] and [e], phoneme / o / as [ɔ] and [o], and phoneme / ə / as [ə].

4. Conclusion

The results obtained from this study are that based on the residence of speakers and the social groups of Javanese speakers in Kebumen District, they have variations of vowel phoneme / a /, / i /, / u /, / e /, / o /, and consonant / b /, / d /, / k /, / g /, as well as variations of sound [r], [h], [-əw-], and [-ək]. The result of variation obtained is phoneme / a / pronounced [a], [ɔ], [ə], and [ɛ]. The phoneme / i / is pronounced [i], [I], and [ɛ]. The phoneme / u / is pronounced [u], and [U]. The phoneme / e / is pronounced [e] and [ɛ]. The phoneme / o / is pronounced [o] and [ɔ]. For the phoneme / b /, / d /, / g /, and / k / pronounced fixed as [b], [d], [g], and [k] which in standard Java is pronounced [p], [t], [k], and [ʔ]. The phoneme / r / can be inserted in the word. Phoneme / h / uninstalled. In addition, the sounds [-əw-] and [-ək] respectively as variants of the [-uw-] and [-aʔ] sounds.

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Analysis technique of translation and measurement shift (shifts) in the text of AXA Life contract Indonesia

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Abstract – The research was carried out to analyse a legislative text as a product of translation. It is referred to Seiddel's qualitative data analysis where the data processing was performed by selecting, identification, and tabulating. (2%), compensation (1%), description (2%) discursive creation (5%) generalization (5%), literal translation (10%), modulation (8%), particularization (5%) reduction (5%) completion (4%), and dilation (14%). Meanwhile, the four categories shift are implemented as the following frequency: Intra-system shifts; 90 (52.02%), followed by Unit Shifts 46 (26.59%), Structural Shifts 24 (13.88%), and then Class Shifts 13 (7.51%). The other finding was inaccurateness. It was found that there were inaccurate translation for 5 phrases, and resulted not equivalence ones in rendering the source language into the target language.

Keywords: *shifts, technique, equivalence*

1. Introduction

Translation is one of the branches of applied linguistics as part of the activity in interpersonal communication with different languages that have been known since ancient Rome in the early centuries. It was precisely in the first century BC (46 BC) when Cicero claimed that translation was meaning languages in general. "In that day translation activities had been practiced over ancient Babylonian manuscripts (scribal activities) more than three thousand years ago (Horby, 1988).

Translation includes several aspects, such as grammatical skill, reading skill, and discourse analysis (Bell, 1991) describes the definition of translation as a process of expression of a language into another language taking into account the semantic and equality or equivalence factors "... translation as" The expression in another language (TL) of what has been expressed in another source, preserving semantic and stylistic equivalences"

"Analysis of Translation and Shift Techniques in AXA-Life Indonesia Contract Text" examines a translation product of the contract text as legal text in terms of translation techniques as well as category shifts as part of the shifting of form and meaning occurring in the process of translation text of AXA-Life Indonesia contract.

Translation is the transition of the source language into the target language in the form of written text" (Munday, 2001) and Catford, 1965). Defines translation as a replacement of the source language text with an equivalent text in the target language. "(TL) and the term equivalent is a clear a key term "In translation there is a transfer of meaning from the source language to the target language, with the accuracy of the message, the legibility, and the acceptability of the product (Nababan, 2010).

Interpreting sense is an attempt intended to restate what one has declared or written in a language into another. "The translation is intended to restate in one language what someone else said or wrote in another language" (Larson, 1984).

Translation is also defined as the transfer of meaning from the source language into the target language through three-step approach: 1) studying the lexicon, grammatical structure, communication situation, and cultural context of the source language text; 2) analyse the source language text to find its meaning; and 3) revealing the same meaning by using appropriate lexicons and grammatical structures in the target language (Baker, 1992).

In addition to the vocabulary and grammar, the translation process also concerns the culture (Hatim, 2001). The complex problem faced by an interpreter, demanding more skills to apply the use of two main pillars as a buffer for translation, namely (1) competence in two languages, (2) expertise in basic knowledge of the text genre and skilfully concluded, and (3) competence in communication (Bell, 1991).

Equivalence boils down to two levels: words, phrases, grammatical, textual, and pragmatic levels with the notion that they remain influenced by various linguistic and cultural factors; which is therefore relative. "It is commonly used as an alternative to the letters" (Baker, 1992).

Mary Snell and Hornby use the term parallel texts as an equivalent substitute. A translation is always obtained from another text; parallel text, which results from two texts independent from the linguistic side and derived from a very identical situation. "A translation is always derived from another text, parallel texts are two linguistically independent product arising from identical situation" (Steiner and Yallop (eds.), 2001).

Non-parallel translation results are an indication of inaccuracies in translation; where there is a mismatch of meaning between the source language and the target language, then such translations include poor translations. "... if a text does not match its source text ideationally, so does the question whether it is a good translation does not rise" (Albir and Molina, 2002).

There are several techniques and shifts in translation such as adaptation, borrowing amplification, calque, translation techniques in which the translator translates literary source language phrases literally, compensation, description, discursive creation, general equivalence, linguistic amplification of linguistic compression (linguistic amplification) linguistic compression, literal translation, modulation, particularization, reduction, substitution, variation, deletion, transposition or transposition (Bhatia, 1993).

A text in discourse is not purely a linguistic phenomenon, but it must also be viewed as a tool in terms of its function, i.e. as a means of communication (Hornby and Snell (1988). This confirms that it takes various techniques to deliver the source language to the target language communicatively, which in this case, the shift of meaning (shifts) is one technique that is absolutely necessary implementation.

The shift in Translation consists of shifting meaning and shift in shape. In the shift of meaning, the form (word, phrase, and clause) is fixed; which shift is the meaning. The meaning of the shift occurs because one word has primary meaning and secondary meaning. It is stated that the meaning must be maintained, while the form may be changed. In this case it is necessary shift technique as an alternative (Hatim, 2001). "To shift from one language to another is to alter the forms. Further, the contrasting forms convey meanings which cannot but fail to coincide totally; there is no absolute synonymy between words in the same language" (Bell, 1992).

Of the two types of shifts are likely to occur category shift or level shift. But the core discussion in this paper is the shift category. Category shift consists of (a) Structural Shift: shift at the level of structure words in clauses that result in a change of meaning on the translation result. Structural shifts, for example, of the Explained-Explained (DM) structured phrase into the Explained-Explained (MD), (b) Class Shift phrase occurs when a particular word type in the source language shifts to another word type in the target language (Comprise shifts from one part of speech to another. (c) Unit Shifts involve change ranks from word to phrase, from phrase to clause and vice versa. This level shift can occur from the source language to the target language or vice versa, and (d) Intra-System Shift occurs when the source and target languages

are in a possess somewhat corresponding systems the translation does not indicate the relation seen in the terms of the target language system (TL). For example: the sum and article systems that although have the same system in English and Indonesian, but both do not always mean the same. The article 'a' in English, in the 'He has a broken leg' clause is not translated as 'He has a broken leg' but 'He broke his leg' or 'broke his leg' in Indonesian as the target language (Munday, 2001).

Tiered shifts occur when transpositions produce different target language elements, whether phonological, graphological, grammatical, or lexical. The shift is caused by the grammar on the source and word (lexis) language of the target language.

Example: Source Language: "John swims on Saturdays"
Target Language: "John swims on Saturdays"

(Simple Present which is marked with 's' on 'swims' shifts to 'every time' on lexeme 'swims').

The contract text is a text that contains binding agreements between two or more parties which usually consist of a series of interrelated parts. "A recognizable communicative event characterized by a set of communicative objectives (s) identified and mutually understood by members of the professional community in which it is regularly" (Bhatia, 1993).

The definition of legal language according to Bhatia refers to the text used to communicate the activities of a particular professional association. Some of them are written text in the form of advocate and client consultations, counsel-fitness examination and legislation, contracts, agreements, and the like (Bhatia, 1993).

2. Method

The source of the research data is the legal text AXA-Life Indonesia as a population, consisting of 25 articles, 51 verses, 102 subparagraphs, and 7 sub-paragraphs, as stuck data. The source language consists of 5,451 words; 27,403 characters; 272 paragraphs; and 576 lines. (Words count; MS-words) While in the Indonesian language as the target language consists of 4,601 words; 29,055 characters; 268 paragraphs. Of the twenty-five articles of the contract document (population), 100 phrases were provided for translation technique studies and 173 phrases for the study of shifts as accidental samples (Bhatia, 1993).

Data analysis refers to the theory of Qualitative Data Analysis through data processing performed in four stages: 1) record by coding, 2) collecting, sorting, classifying, and 3) indexing, and 4) to think, by creating categories of data, interpreting, and making general findings (Moleong, 2002).

The application of the theory is by the steps of work: 1) Identification of words, phrases, and / or clauses through various translation techniques chronologically, 2) Identify shifts that occur in the whole text, 3) Editing in the form

of examination of the entire translation of the source language to the target language, and 4) Tabulation of compilation and calculation of data of editing result, then presented in the form of frequency table and then held the calculation in percentage (%).

Data analysis by identification based on translation techniques and the four types of shifts. The results are shown through tables and diagrams. Analysis refers to two variables, namely; 1) the variant of translation techniques and 2) the four types of shifts. The results are summarized, displayed statistically and followed by descriptive explanations in the results and discussion sections.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Model Technical Translation on Contract Text

Source Language	Language Target
<i>The board of arbitration may amend this timetable from time to time.</i>	Dewan Arbitrase memiliki wewenang untuk mengubah jadwal setiap saat.

The board of arbitration may amend this timetable from time to time. The Arbitration Board has the authority to change the schedule at any time.

In the translation of the above clause, the 'may' lexeme is implicit information which is then translated by applying the amplification technique i.e. paraphrasing may be 'authorized to ...'

3.2 Shift Model on Contract Text Translation

Class Shift

Source Language	Language Target
<i>They insist on higher wages, better living conditions and shorter working hours.</i>	Mereka menuntut kenaikan gaji, perbaikan syarat-syarat kehidupan dan pengurangan jam kerja.

They insist on higher wages, better living conditions and shorter working hours. They demanded a raise, improved living conditions and reduced working hours.

The higher, better, and shorter adjectives shift to noun, increase and decrease.

Table 1 Frequency of Application of Translation Technique

Num.	Translation Phrase	Clause/ Technique	
		Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Amplification	37	37%
2	Lending	2	2%

3	Calque	2	2%
4	Compensation	1	1%
5	Description	2	2%
6	Discursive Creations	5	5%
7	Generalization	5	5%
8	Literal Translation	10	10%
9	Modulation	8	8%
10	Particular	5	5%
11	Reduction	5	5%
12	Additions	4	4%
13	Removals	14	14%
		100	100%

Table 3 Frequency of Shifting in Translation

Num.	Category Shifts	Clause/ Technique	
		Amount	Percentage (%)

1	Structural Shift	24	13,88%
2	Class Shifts	13	7,51%
3	Unit Shifts	46	26,59%
4	Intra-System Shifts	90	52,02%
	Amount Clause/ Technique	173	100%

The frequency of shifting as a result of the analysis of the entire AXA-Life Indonesia contract text is illustrated in the following chart.

3.3 Inequalities of Translation

Inaccuracies in the translation process should be avoided in order to avoid distortion or even loss of source language meaning in the translation text. Inaccuracies can occur with the occurrence of paraphrasing by adding, omitting, and obscuring the meaning of the source language in the target language. This occurs in the legal-text translation process of AXA-Life Indonesia, albeit only in a very small percentage.

Inaccuracy occurs in the phrase 'corresponding meaning' which translates to 'correspondence', 'No partnership translates to' cooperation', 'shall be deemed 'translated into' obliging " between the parties 'translated' by the parties ', and' grace period 'is inconsistently translated, i.e.' grace period 'and' free period '

Besides that, there is a lack of precision interpretation when translating "policy anniversary" into "policy anniversary" which actually can be interpreted more accurately with the phrase: "policy due date" and in force majeure translation which is translated with force majeure. In terms of legibility and acceptability, the phrase force majeure is more accurate if interpreted by "emergency conditions" rather than "majesty" which means arbitrary (Big Indonesian Dictionary 1990: 376)

In general, in translation of the AXA-Life Indonesia contract text, several techniques and shifts have been applied as a dynamic effort aimed at obtaining equivalent, legible and acceptable translation products.

4. Conclusion

The amplification: 37%, (2) lending: 2%, (3) calque: 2%, (4) Compensation: 1%, (5) description: 2%, (6) discursive creations: 5%, (7) generalization: 5%, (8) literal translation: 10%, (9) modulation: 8%, (10) 5%, (11) reduction: 5%, (12) additions: 4%, and (13) removal: 14%.

Of the 13 types of translation techniques applied, the highest frequency technique is the Amplification technique (37%). Meanwhile, among the four types of shifts according to Catford's theory, Intra-System shift is the most dominant shift in translation of AXA-Life Indonesia contract text (52%).

The four types of category shifts are applied to the translation process of AXA-Life Indonesia contract text. The most dominant shift is intra-system shifts (first in-line shifts); (Shifts) of 26.59% (13), Structural Shifts 13.88% (24) and Class Shifts of 7.51% (13). There is inaccuracy in the process of translation of AXA Life's contract text, where there are five cases of inaccuracies in translation that result in unequal translation.

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The Design and development of model of English training program for local community at rural tourism

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Abstract – The President of Republic of Indonesia issued eight instructions at the Cabinet Forum on January 4th 2016, one of which was “Ensuring the Development of the 10 National Tourism Destinations or 10 New Bali, to meet the 2019 tourism target, the increasing of national income from 120 billion into 240 billion. Bali as one of Indonesia’s prime tourism destination has also taken participation in increasing the income. This can be seen from the support given by Bali government to establish the development program of ten rural tourism in the program of the development of Bali in tourism for the next four years to develop the rural tourism. Based on this, the research was aimed at participating in the development of Human Resource in areas where rural tourism take place to allow the villagers to interact intensively with foreign tourists and give their best service. The participation was the design and development of English training with syllabus, lesson plan and training material as its results. The training put much emphasis on the increase of English communication ability based on the potential resource of Bedulu Village as one of rural tourism. The method of the research was Design and Development, proposed by Ellis and Levy (2010), that consists of several phases in designing and developing English training. It is expected that the output of the study will result in the realization of society service at rural tourism as English training.

Keywords: *designing, development, model of English training, tourism village*

1. Introduction

The president of the Republic of Indonesia issued eight instructions at the Cabinet Forum January 4th 2016, one of which was “ensure development of the 10 national tourism destination”, or “creating the 10 new Bali”, such as Lake Toba Tanjung Kelayang, Tanjung Lesung, Kepulauan Seribu, Borobudur, Bromo Tengger, Semeru, Mandalika, Labuan Bajo, Wakatobi, Morotai. This is to fulfill the tourism macro target, which are a) increasing the contribution of PDB (WTTC) from 9% (Rp 945.09 trillion into 15%, b) increasing the foreign tourism from 9 million to 20 million and c) increasing domestic tourists from 250 million to 275 million (Subhiksu, 2013). The Indonesian tourism is supported by the cabinet of President Jokowi. It will see its better future.

As one of Indonesia’s major tourism destination, Bali takes participation in the growth of economy of the village society. This can be seen from Bali’s government support to establish the development program of 100 village in the program of the development of Bali in tourism for the upcoming 4 years to develop rural tourism destination (Sastrayuda, 2010).

Community Based on tourism Development like rural tourism can increase the availability of job vacancy from eleven million into 13 million, and therefore overcomes the economical discrepancy due to the local community will have enormous opportunity to work in tourism sector (Mudayen, and Lantum, 2008).

One of training to improve the local community readiness in interacting with foreign visitors is language training, besides other trainings. A research carried on an analysis on HR development of rural tourism participant in Bantul Regency. The research stated that most villagers stated their needs of specific foreign language is English, which reached 92%. The other foreign languages has not yet been determined as a specific need (Sari et al, 2015).

Based on the government’s instruction at Cabinet Forum on January 4 2016, about the enhancement of ten national tourism destinations, and the role of Bali local government to run the program of developing 100 tourism villages in the program of the development of Bali in tourism sector for the upcoming 4 years, this research is aimed at designing and developing the model of syllabus, lesson plan and material of English training for villagers, emphasizing on English for communication at rural tourism.

The result of the study is expected to be beneficial for the people in the tourism village in improving their ability to communicate in English with foreign tourism, English instructors in preparing English training at tourism village, English lecture in doing one of the *Tri Dharma Perguruan Tinggi* which is the social service activity.

Several previous study which was used as literature review is (Wijayanti et al, 2015) that the research concerns on English training aimed for guide and homestay owner at Munduk village, Buleleng. It was discovered that most of the homestay owner do not have sufficient English ability to provide the best service for foreign tourist. The other research was that dealing with ability in speaking (Tomlison, 2012). The research discovered the lack of ability in speaking English among homestay owners at Kandri tourism village, Semarang. Their education level was assumed to be one factor, as well as their age. Wijayanti then designed a drill and repetition based English training to equip them with readiness to communicate with foreign tourist.

The result was the increase of English ability shown by the homestay owner. Also made available to them was a handbook to assist in tourist service.

The operational definition based on the concept is Design and Development model, which refers to effort by writer, teachers, or students to give input on language and exploitate the provided source to maximize the probability of usage (Richey and Klein, 2007), secondly, it is the concept of English training, which is a process to help people obtain skill and knowledge (Ellis and Levy, 2010), in this case is knowledge of English that will give positive impacts on social, education and career (Howard and Major, 2005). Thirdly, it is the concept of rural village, which is a particular effort to make available for visitor some private contact, the feeling of physical environment in rural area and then the tourist is given opportunity to participate in various activities, tradition and local lifestyle. The visitor can experience unique and intangible features which is authentic and original such as local friendliness of several countries and religion, population at certain area has developed a specific way of life (Benard and Viney 1991).

The theory used to analyze and create the design and development of English training at tourism village is Design and Development, which has been developed by several experts. The Design and Development research is said to be a systematical process on design, development and evaluation to construct empirical base to create product and instructional and non-instructional tools as well as a new or refined model owned by the government (Kazar and Mede, 2014). There were six steps of DnD Research (Koyan et al, 2012).

2. Method

This research used a theory proposed by Koyan et al (2012) in designing and developing the training model of English training for people at rural tourism. The subject of the research was the research informant, the local community of Bedulu, Gianyar Bali, after doing problem identification through need analysis with the experts, people representatives and the representative of POKDARWIS at Bedulu Village who participate in the development of a rural tourism. The object of the study is the product of design and development used as the model of English training as foreign language for local community at rural tourism.

The data was collected based on the theory of Design and Development research, proposed by Koyan et al (2012) through the following procedure: a) identifying the problem to motivate the research by using need analysis at Bedulu Village, b) explaining the aim of the research, c) designing and developing the model of English training in the form of syllabus, lesson plan and training material, d) examining the design and development model through FGD with the expert in tourism and English language teaching, e) evaluating and revising the result of design and development model based on FGD, f) communicating the output in the design and development of English training through presentation and publication at scientific journal.

3. Results and Discussion

Below is the result of the design and development of syllabus, lesson plan and English material.

Syllabus Beginner Level Duration: 16 meetings x 1.5 hours (60 hours)						
Day	Topic	Function	Expression	Structure	Speaking / Listening	Reading / Writing
1, 2	Greeting and Introducing Guests	Greeting, Introducing yourself, introducing someone	Good morning.... My name is... Her name is...	Subjective pronoun Adjective pronoun	Personal information	
		Checking Information Exchanging personal information, Saying hello and goodbye	Where are you from..? Are you American..?	Wh-question Verb be: is, am, are contraction		
Lesson Plan (Beginner Level)						
Meeting 1						
Action		Topic: Greeting and Introducing Guests				Time needed
Warmer		Playing 'Whisper Race'				15 minutes
Introducing Topic		Identifying some language functions for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greeting • Introducing oneself • Introducing someone to someone else 				25 minutes
Activities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to the example of conversation • Creating conversation • Role play • Doing exercises 				40 minutes
Teacher's Note: Students will be able to greet and introduce themselves						
Meeting 2						
Action		Topic: Checking and Exchanging Information				Time needed
Warmer		Playing 'Snow Ball'				15 minutes
Introducing Topic		Identifying some language functions for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Checking Information • Exchanging personal information • Saying hello and goodbye 				25 minutes
Activities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to the example of conversation • Creating conversation 				40 minutes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role play • Doing exercises 	
Teacher's Note: Students will be competence in welcoming the guest		

Material Development
Beginner Level
Day 1: Greeting and Introducing to Guests

I. Introducing yourself

Fill the blanks in the conversation and practice it

my	his	her	is	are	you	too	me	him	am	it
----	-----	-----	----	-----	-----	-----	----	-----	----	----

Jack : David, who is standing there?
 David : Oh. That (1) my father. (2). name is John.
 Jack : Could you introduce me to (3).
 David : sure
 Jack : good morning, Mr. John. (4). name (5) Jack
 Mr. John : Call (6). John. Where (7). you from?
 Jack : I (8). from Australia. Nice to meet (9).
 Mr. John : Nice to meet you (10).

PRONOUNS			
Subject	Object	Possessive	Possessive
Pronouns	Pronouns	Adjectives	Pronouns
I	me	my	mine
You	you	your	yours
He	him	his	his
She	her	her	hers
It	it	its	its
We	us	our	ours
You	you	your	yours
They	them	their	theirs

II. Make four sentences using subject pronouns, object pronouns, possessive adjective and possessive pronouns

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

III. Preposition and verb be. Correct the following sentences

1. My father are a farmer.
2. Bedulu village am located in Gianyar
3. He is we friend.
4. They is here last month.
5. The chef have made some tasty food.

Day 2: Checking and Exchanging Information

I. Greeting

How would you greet your guests in the following situations? Use Sir, Madam, Miss, Ladies or Gentleman, and greet them with good morning, good afternoon, goodbye or goodnight

1. A woman aged about 25 at 12.30 pm
2. A married couple at 10 pm
3. Four men in the restaurant at 11.00 pm
4. Say goodbye to a woman and 2 men at 9 pm
5. A young lady at midnight

II. Introducing Yourself

Match the question in column A with the response in column B.

A How do you pronounce your first name? Excuse me, what's your first name again? How do you spell your last name? What do people call you?	B W-A-Y-A-N It's Smith Well, everyone calls me Gus De Oh, it's Putu
---	--

III. Conversation

Complete these conversations. Then practice with a partner

- A. you from the Bali?
 B. Yes, I , from Gianyar.
 A. Putu in the market?
 B. No, she , in the garden.
 A: you and Komang from Tabanan?
 B: Yes, we , from Kediri.

Syllabus						
Pre-Intermediate Level						
Duration: 16 meetings X 1.5 hours (60 hours)						
Day	Topic	Function	Expression	Grammar	Speaking/ listening	Writing / reading
1, 2	Talking past event	Talking about past events	We drove to the lake city Where do you go?	Past simple; statement, wh-question Regular/irregular		
		Talking about vacations	Was your brother.... Were you at home....	Past simple with be		
3,4	Describing places	Asking about and describing locations of places;	There is a post office at the corner Is there a bank around here	There is/there are Is there/are there Preposition of place; at, on, in	Description of places in neighborhood	
		Asking about quantities	I have some money She hasn't any money There are some oranges...	Countable/uncountable Quantifier; some, any, much, many. question with; how		

				much, how many		
		Evaluating city services; asking for and giving information	Could you tell me where the post office is? Do you know when the buses leave from the city	Indirect question from wh-question Useful expression; let me think,, It's close to... It's next to		Writing a description of transportation service

Lesson Plan Pre-Intermediate Level		
Action	Topic: Past memories	Time needed
Warmer	Recalling childhood memories	15 minutes
Introducing Topic	Identifying some language functions for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Past Tense • Used to 	25 minutes
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to a conversation • Telling a story about one's childhood • Past tense exercises 	40 minutes
Teacher's Note: Students will be able to express his/her past experience		
Meeting 2		
Action	Topic: Traffic	Time needed
Warmer	Matching words	15 minutes
Introducing Topic	Describing Places	25 minutes
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to the example of conversation • Creating conversation • Role play • Doing exercises 	40 minutes
Teacher's Note: Students will be able to ask and give information		

Material Development (Pre-Intermediate Level)	
Day1: A Time to Remember	
I. Practice the conversation	
Putu	: Good morning, Mr. Green. How are you?
Green	: Oh, I'm fine, but little tired.
Putu	: What did you do yesterday?
Green	: I had a whole day tour yesterday. I went to Ubud and Kintamani.
Putu	: Really, how was your trip?
Green	: It was really fantastic. I have never gone to the place before. Me and my family enjoyed trip.
II. Answer the question below!	
a. Who are the characters in the conversation?	

- b. Where did Mr. Green go for trip yesterday?
 c. How was Mr. Green trip?

III. Grammar focus

Past tense. Use the simple pas to talk about activities or events in the past

- Where **did** you go yesterday? I **went** to Sanur festival yesterday
 What **did** she do last week? She **visited** Neka Museum last week
 Where **were** they two days ago? They **were** in Kuta two days ago
Did Wayan serve the guest well? Yes, he **did** / no, he **didn't (did not)**
Were you in Ubud? Yes, I **was**/ no, I **wasn't (was not)**

IV. Complete the conversation. Then practice

- A: could you tell me about your vacation? Where (do) you go?
 B: Well, I (visit)Bali Zoo Park at Singapadu village. I (see)many kinds of animal over there. There (be) many kind of birds, tigers, apes and many more.
 A: (do)you take many picture?
 B: Of course, I (do).
 A: What (do) you do next?
 B: Then, I (go)to Sukawati art market. I bought some souvenir in the market. They (be) many kind of sarongs, t shirt and other souvenirs.
 A: (do) you try some Balinese food?
 B: No, I (not). Balinese food is spicy.

Used to

Used to is something regularly did in the past but don't do anymore

Example

- When I was a kid, we **used to** visit Kuta Beach
Did you **use to** have a hobby?
 Yes, I **use to** surf at Kuta Beach
 What place **did** you **use to** visit?
 I **used to** visit Tegal Lalang village

V. Memories

Write five sentences about yourself using used to. Do you and your partner have anything in common?

- a. What is your favourite memory?
 b. What sport or game did you use to play?
 c. Did you use to have a nickname?
 d. Where did you use to spend your holiday?
 e. Did you use to have a part time job?

VI. Writing

- A. Write about the thing you used to do, use some ideas from exercise 3, then compare take turns reading your composition aloud.

Day 2: It's Too Much Traffic!

I. Word Power

- A. Match the nouns in column A and B to make a compound nouns

Bus + stop = bus stop

- | | |
|---------|----------|
| A | B |
| Traffic | entrance |
| Bus | light |
| Bicycle | station |
| Stop | sign |
| Taxi | jam |

II. Conversation.

Practice the conversation.

Putu : why is there never a bus when you want one?

Wayan : there aren't enough buses on this route

Putu : sometime I like to write a letter on the newspaper.

Wayan : good idea, you should say that we need more bus line.

Putu : and fewer motorbikes. There are too many motorbikes in the city

Wayan : yeah, there is too much pollution in the city.

III. Grammar Focus

Adverb of Quantity

Adverb of quantity tell you how much or how many of noun either countable or uncountable noun.

With countable noun

There are **too many** motorbikes

There **aren't enough** buses

There **should be fewer** cars

with uncountable noun

there is too much traffic

there **isn't enough** parking

there **should be less** pollution

Complete these statement about transportation problem.

- There are motorbikes
- There should be cars in the city
- There should be pollution in the city
- There are cars parked on the street
- There is enough public transportation in the city

IV. Writing

Write about the transportation problems in your city.

The result of the study was to answer the DnD Research theory proposed by Ellis, which includes: a) identifying the problems through observation, interview and FGD with experts, the representative of POKDARWIS, and the local community of Bedulu, Gianyar, b) explaining of the goal of the research as in Chapter I, c) designing and developing syllabus, lesson plan and training material, d) examining the design and development through FGD with one language expert and one tourism expert as well as with language teachers, e) evaluating the result of the design and development of the model of syllabus, lesson plan and English teaching material through a FGD with the expert and English lecturers from several universities and colleges, f) communicating the outcome of the research which covers the design and development of English training model through presentation, seminar and publication at scientific journal.

4. Conclusion

The outcome of the research was the model of syllabus, lesson plan and English training material for local community at tourism village. The English training emphasize on the increase of communication ability based on the potential resource of Bedulu village. The training material is developed into English training handout entitled 'English for Rural Tourism'. This handout can be used for English training program to implement 'Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat' at rural tourism.

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Codes mixing between buyers and mobile phone hackers in Bekasi, West Java

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Abstract – This review discusses the code mixing that occurs on talks between a sales clerk and four buyers at a mobile phone shop located in a business centre in the central Bekasi, West Java. The data collection is done by recording conversations between four buyers and one the store saleswoman. Data was analysed qualitatively to obtain a comprehensive research result that aims to determine the type, level, nature, and causal factors of code interference. The results showed: (1) There are three types of code mixings that occur, namely external code-mixing, internal code-mixing and mixed code-mixing. The most common is external code-mixing, especially from English to Indonesian language. (2). The most common form of code-mixing is in the word level. (3). The cause of code interference is caused by several factors, namely the limitation factor in the mastery of vocabulary in the source language, to show the familiarity and habit factor of the speaker.

Keywords: *code mixing, interference, linguistics, non linguistics*

1. Introduction

Code-mixing often occurs in multilingual societies as well as people living in cities such as Jakarta, Bandung and Surabaya. Similarly in the city of Bekasi geographically directly adjacent to the capital of our country Jakarta events code mixing is also often the case. Bekasi residents can be said to be very diverse and heterogeneous. In addition to indigenous people, residents in the city of Bekasi come from various remote homeland such as from Java, Sumatra, Sulawesi, Kalimantan and even from Papua. The population growth in Bekasi city is very significant along with the rapid growth of industrial sector both in Bekasi city and Bekasi regency which is directly adjacent to Bekasi city. The total population of Bekasi city in 2010 was 2,384,032 people increased by 14.65% to 2,733,240 inhabitants by 2015. (<https://bekasikota.bps.go.id/linkTabelStatis/view/id/47>). The diversity of tribes and the language contained in the city of Bekasi resulted in a variety of languages used by residents of Bekasi in daily communication in addition to the Indonesian language. The diversity of languages used in this communication often causes Code Mixings between Indonesian and regional languages, Indonesian language with foreign languages and also between local languages with one other regional language. For example, the use of the word 'download' in the following sentence: "Andi, have you please download the article about the event of ISIS attacks in Marawi?" Similarly in the phrase "Santi, what time Lion Air plane will take off from Kualanamu airport?" The above code mixing is called internal code-mixing because the speakers mix the foreign language elements in this case English, i.e. the word 'download' and 'take off' instead of the so-called code mix between English and Indonesian. The speakers include the element of the word 'download' in English into Indonesian instead of 'download' and 'take off'.

In addition to inter-language, code mixing can also occur between different languages, from the variety of formal languages to the various informal languages, as in the following sentence. "Rina, can you explain the incident to my father 'entar' in the afternoon?" In that sentence the speaker uses the word 'entar' which is not formal rather than the more formal 'later' word. In addition to the use of languages, dialects and languages, code intervening events can occur based on place and time, as well as in markets, ports, tire factories and conference buildings. In this paper, the authors want to examine the type, nature and causes of code interference events between buyers and clerks of mobile phone shops in a shop in Bekasi, West Java.

To support the study of this code mix, the author uses several theories relevant to this code mix, among them theories of bilingualism and language interference.

Bilingualism or bilingualism is a situation where people can communicate in two languages ^[10]. The multi-ethnic condition of Indonesian society and the diversity of regional languages also resulted in the tendency of Indonesians to be bilingual because in addition to being able to speak in the local language as their mother tongue, Indonesian people also have the obligation to master the Indonesian language as the official language and the language of the country used in schools, trade, and to communicate daily. In addition to regional and Indonesian languages and the

influence of technological developments in this global era, proficiency in foreign languages, such as English, French, and Mandarin is very important. This condition enable most Indonesian people not only to be bilingual but also multi-lingual because of their ability to use more than two languages, namely the local language, Indonesian language and foreign languages. The use of two or more languages often causes mixing between elements of one language to another. It is stated that if a speaker uses two or more languages it can be said that the languages are in contact (Suwito, 1983). Bilingualism and multilingualism are closely related to code mixing.

Interference is a mistake caused by the practice of pronunciation of a language to another language that includes the pronunciation of sound units, grammar, and vocabulary (Chaer and Agustina.1995). Similarly, interference is a deviation of the norm from one or more languages (Chaer, 1994). However, Nababan (1984) stated that interference is caused by habits of incorporating a mother tongue or dialect into a second language or dialect. Interference is the contact of language, the limitations of the city's vocabulary, the need for word equality, and the prestige of the source language. In addition, the decline in allegiance to the recipient language is also a contributing factor to the interference (Sumarsono, 2002: Sumarsono and Partana, 2004; Wardhaugh, 2004).

In contrast to interference, integration is the use of language elements of a particular language against other languages and has been considered to be part of the language, so it is no longer referred to as the lending element (Chaer, 1994). In integration, it is stated that the absorption element is no longer visible as a foreign language element because the element of absorption has been adjusted to the system or rules of absorbent language. Interference is temporary and integration is permanent.

Based on the linguistic aspect, "Indonesian society is a bilingual society (bilingual) that controls more than one language that is regional language, Indonesian, and foreign language" (Mahsun, 2007). The bilingual community will experience language contact so that it gives birth code mixing. According^[1], any speech events that take place over several speech acts will involve several things, such as speakers and speakers, the language medium, and the purpose of the conversation. He explains that code mixings are the mixing of two languages or languages in a single act of language without anything in the language situation that requires mixing of languages (Mahsun, 2007). The definition of code mixing, according Mahsun (2007), is a mixing of two languages or more in a language act without any situation that demands the mixing. Similarly Suwito (1983)¹ argues code mixing occurs when elements of a single language are incorporated into another language that takes place consistently both wording elements, phrases as well as clauses. In addition, code mixings can occur when speakers insert elements of other languages into a particular language (Dornyei, 2007).

Based on the element of absorption, code mixing is classified into three parts. The first is called the outer code mix (outer code mixing), which is a mix of code that absorbs foreign language elements (Sumarsono, 2002: Sumarsono and Partana, 2004). The second is called code mixing into (inner code mixing), which is a mixture of

languages between languages in a single national language, between dialect in a regional language, or between varieties and language styles contained in one dialect. For example, an Indonesian speaker inserts elements of regional languages such as Manado into Indonesian or vice versa. The third is called code-mixing Mixing that is a mixture of a national language, regional languages and foreign languages. There are two driving factors behind the interference of code, i.e. attitudinal type or non-linguistic background and linguistic type (Suwito, 1983; Sumarsono, 2002). The Non-Focus Factor aims to soften the speech, indicate the level or social position, and indicate a new cultural influence while the linguistic factor aims to facilitate choosing words, avoiding ambiguous meanings, and influencing others. Based on the theory, this research wanted to know how form, type and cause of code mix that happened in a mobile phone in Bekasi.

2. Method

To get a comprehensive overview of the use of code mix in buying and selling conversations between four consumers and a saleswoman at a mobile phone shop in Bekasi, West Java, a qualitative research using the method is used. The method used to refer to data obtained by listening to the use of language and record conversations between shop clerks with the buyer. After the conversation data is recorded the next step is to make a transcription of the conversation and select which part of the conversation contains code mixing for analysis.

Qualitative research is used because the data in this study is not a number but is an utterance. Qualitative research relates to a set of data consisting of interview recordings, various types of texts (e.g. field notes, journals, diaries, documents) and pictures (photographs or videos). The research is focused on obtaining the type and code mixings as well as factors causing code mixings based on data obtained from recording of conversations between consumers and shop-shop salespeople at Mall Metropolitan Bekasi, West Java.

Data collection and data analysis was done with the following steps.

- 1) Record the data and transcribe it.
- 2) Identify and classify the data based on the type and form of code mix that occurs, i.e. word, phrase or clause.
- 3) Look for the causes of code mixing.
- 4) Drawing conclusions.

Based on the theory that has been described above, this research will be focused on three things, namely to know the mix of code that occurs based on the shape, type and cause of the code mixing.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of data analysis that has been done can be classified according to type, level, nature, and causal factors of code interference as follows.

3.1 Mix the code by shape

1). Code Mixing in the form of words

M = buyer (consisting of M-1, M-2, M-3, M-4)

PT = Shop clerk

Code Mixings from foreign languages, regional languages and Indonesian non-standard varieties can be found in the use of words as contained in the following Data (1) and Data (4).

Data (1)

M-1: Hmmm this is mbak, I want to service hp, if you make download, how slow
yes....

In Data (1), the buyer (M-1) uses a word-shaped mix of 'mbak', 'hp', 'download', and 'lemot'. The word 'mbak' derived from the Javanese language has the meaning of 'sister' in the Indonesian language. The word 'mbak' is included in the word greeting addressed to a woman by a person either by a man or a woman while the word 'lemot' is a form of a raw Indonesian acronym from 'weak brain' meaning 'slow'. The word and 'download' and 'hp' (abbreviated form of 'handphone') are from English. Both words are in Indonesian in a row have meaning 'mobile phone' and 'download'.

Data (4)

M-1: I tried yesterday..network is good but still cannot. Use wifi
also cannot ... how *tuh*?

In Data (4), the word 'network' comes from English used by the buyer (M-1) instead of using the word 'network'. The word 'wifi' comes from the English shorthand form, ie wireless fidelity which has the meaning of 'wireless network' whereas the word 'gimana' and 'tuh' comes from the non-standard Indonesian language whose meanings are 'how' and 'it' respectively.

3.2 Compound Code is a phrase

Code Mixings from foreign languages, Javanese and Indonesian languages can be found in the use of phrases as contained in the following Data (16) and Data (18).

Data (16)

M-2: *Yo nek jenenge* 'customer service' ... B 's most ... *7 lah* .. 8! (Yes that is the name of the shopkeeper may be a B value, roughly a value of 7 ... or 8!)

Code Mixing that occurs in the data (16) above is a mixture of English phrases into the Java language. The phrase 'customer service' comes from English meaning 'customer'

Data 18

M-1: Oooooo ya already ... by the *waymanggilnya* do not father dong! Mas only let more familiar ... hmm may ask no hp her not?

In the data (18) above, the buyer (M-1) uses the phrase in English 'by the way' instead of 'by the way' in communicating with shop clerk (PT).

3. 3 Code Mixing is a clause

The Code Mixing event in the clause form is contained in the following sentence.

Data (14)

M-3: Wow means *ditukokkekeypad'e all wae, Yo*.

In that sentence there is a clause of the Java language '*ditukokke* (keypad) e all *wae*' which means is 'all just bought keypad it'.

3.2 Type of Code Mixing

1) Internal Code Mixing

Internal code interfaces are found in the following sentences.

Data 2

PT: May I see his mobile phone pack?

M-1: OK..please ... this *mbak*, .. mango

The use of the word 'mbak' and 'mango' (Javanese) instead of 'kak' and 'please' indicates that the buyer wants to invite the shop clerk (PT) to check his mobile phone. In this case the buyer (M-1) incorporates elements of the Java language (local language) into Indonesian language.

2) External Code Mixing

The use of foreign language elements results in external code interference. Mix this external code can be seen in the following sentence.

Data (7)

PT: If you want to upgrade cost 100 thousand ... but this I check first ... because other applications are too slow ... the touchscreen is also lacking this weekend see the batteries also dah bloated.

In this quote it appears that the elements of English words 'upgrade' and 'touchscreen' are used by the salesperson (PT) to buyers instead of the word 'enhanced' and 'touch screen'. The selection of the word 'upgrade' and 'touchscreen' seems to be more often heard than the word 'boost' and 'touch screen'. Another example can be found in the following quotation.

Data (13)

M-3: Means fluent yes if using internet-an.

M-4: yes, so this hotspot can connect from your tablet. So you do not need to buy a modem anymore.

The use of the word 'internet' which comes from English seems to still be popular used by Indonesian speakers and has not been translated into Indonesian. Based on the Electronic Language Dictionary 2008 (2008), the word 'internet' stands for interconnection-networking is an electronic communication network that connects computer networks and computer facilities organized around the world by telephone or satellite. In Data (13) above, M-3) and use the word 'internet' in communicating with the buyer (M-4). In contrast, the buyer (M-4) uses other English elements, such as the word 'hotspot', 'tablet', 'laptop', and 'modem' with the other person, the buyer (M-3). The word 'hotspot' is a term for an area where one can access the internet network wirelessly as long as it uses personal computers (PCs), laptops, notebooks or gadgets, such as mobile phones or other devices with WiFi (Wireless Fidelity) features.

The word 'tablet' is a complete portable computer that is entirely a flat touch screen. The most prominent feature of a tablet is the use of the screen as input devices that use the tip of the fingers, stylus, and pen digital. In addition, the size of the tablet is relatively smaller when compared with PC or laptop computer code. The word 'modem' (from English is an acronym for demodulator modulator). Generally a modem is used to convert analogy signals to digital and vice versa. The word 'Laptop' is a small, portable personal computer that can be placed on the user's lap, composed over a device that includes a keyboard, display screen, microprocessor, usually equipped with a rechargeable battery.

3). Code Mixing

Data (14)

M-3: Wow means *ditukokkekeypad'e sekwawae, yo*.

In the above quote, the buyer (M-3) mixes both language vocabulary of English 'keypad' and the Java language '*ditukokke*' and '*wae*' with the Indonesian language with his friend.

Based on the data obtained in the process of buying and selling a mobile phone in one of the stores in Bekasi, the factors causing the interference code that is:

1) Factor of vocabulary

The Code Mixing events caused by inadequate vocabulary mastery can be seen in the following sentence.

Data (5)

PT: Yes already ... I check the settings first ... maybe setting a GPRS it is there wrong.

Data (5) above shows that the shop clerk (PT) uses the term 'GPRS' to buyers because the equivalent of the word is not in Indonesian vocabulary. Similarly, the buyer (M-1) in his conversation with the salesperson (PT) incorporates elements of English into Indonesian, as in the following sentence.

Data (6)

M-1: If you make whatsapp slow too, what should be upgraded *aja ya mbak* ... guess how much?

From the above data (6), we see that the buyer (M-1) uses the word 'whatsapp' and 'upgrade', because the buyer (M-1) has difficulty finding the equivalent of both words in Indonesian.

2) Showing intimacy between speakers and hearers

Event Code Mixing can also be caused by the intention and effort between speakers with partners said to establish a more intimate atmosphere. In a conversation between the buyer and a cell phone shop salesman in Bekasi also found the event Code Mixing, as in the following sentence.

Data (2)

PT: May I see his mobile phone pack?

M-1: OK..please ... this is *mbak..mangga*

The buyer (M-1) invites the saleswoman to view his mobile phone by inserting a Javanese vocabulary 'mango' which means 'please' in order to establish intimacy among those who both understand the Javanese language. By establishing intimacy between speakers and speakers can create smoother communication.

Code Mixing events to show intimacy between speakers and speakers are contained in the following sentence quotation.

Data (14)

M-3: Wow means *ditukokkekeypad'e sekwawae, yo.*

Javanese language '*keukad*' (keypad) e all *wae* '(which is pronounced by a student to his friend in a mobile phone shop shows the existence of emotional closeness between them. The use of the Javanese language element also aims to keep intimacy among those who share the same culture and local language.

3). The habit factor

The interruption of codes from regional languages and foreign languages into Indonesian can also be attributed to the habitual factor of speakers as well. Examples can be seen in the following sentence.

Data 4

M-1: I tried yesterday..network is good but still cannot. Use wifi also cannot ... how tuh?

Data 15

M-2: Is there a Jon keypad on it? (Is that Jon's keypad?)

The use of the word 'network', 'how', 'tuh' and 'emang' instead of 'network', 'how', 'that' and 'indeed' respectively by buyers (M-1 and M-2) habits of them using the word.

4. Conclusion

Based on the data analysis above, the event code mixing of buying and selling conversation between mobile phone shop clerk at Metropolitan Mall of Bekasi can be concluded as follows.

1. There are three forms of code mixing, i.e. mix the code in the form of words, mix the code in the form of phrases, and mix the code in the form of clauses.

2. By type, there is a mix of internal code, mixed with external code and also Code Mixing mix. In this study, the interesting thing is the amount of mixed external code especially from English to Indonesian language. This is caused by In addition, the speakers who are students who at the time was completing the undergraduate study (S-1) in the English study program. Another thing because there are two speakers is a Javanese tribe who is also fluent in Javanese.

3. The causes of code interference in the conversation include several factors, namely vocabulary mastery factor in language, to indicate familiarity and the third is caused by the habitual factor of the speaker. Speakers and speakers in this case a saleswoman and some people who visit the mobile phone shop tend to have difficulty in finding the equivalent of English words and terms in the Indonesian language. Caused by limitations in this study, the authors wish for both similar and more complex studies in the broader realm to find the forms, types, and causes of code interference that often occur among people both in Bekasi and Indonesia.

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Existence of Acehese expression in culture of Indonesian speech community

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Abstract – The existence of the Acehese expression in the culture of the Indonesian speech community is a sociolinguistic study. This study was aimed to describe the function of the Acehese expression used by Indonesian speakers. Method of describing the existence of expression using qualitative approach of descriptive type. The Acehese language expression data was collected from the informant using a note. The results of this study indicate that the Acehese expression has a certain function in society so that the expression is used when communicating. The functions vary in order to establish loyalty, fairness, tranquility, and to maintain a balance of life. The Acehese phrase exists in the Indonesian speaking community because it has a continuity between communication and its implementation in the life of society. The existence of this phrase is used as a social critique, guidance, and advice to streng the nunity and unity with in the frame work of Indonesian culture. This expression exists for speakers of the Indonesian language because it contains the power of value that is able to educate speakers unconsciously and thoroughly.

Keywords: *existence, Acehese expression, speakers of the Indonesian language*

1. Introduction

Language is a means of communication to convey ideas, opinions and feelings to others. The delivery of a particular purpose is often done indirectly or using expressions or idioms. Many considerations in communication use phrases, among them to avoid offense. Strictly speaking, it can be said that expression is one way of communication in society to convey ideas, opinions and feelings to others in an unusual way (Setyonegoro, 2013).

The meaning in the expression is implied and is generally profound. The meaning is unpredictable as the meaning of the word in general with the rules of language grammar and semantic theory concerned. The phrase has a meaning that has been conventionally defined by the speakers of the language in question and usually cannot be traced to the meaning generated based on the combined meaning of the word formers of the phrase according to the rules of grammar (Suryadimulya, 2007). Read the following phrase!

Bèklagèèkmanôksuim
'Do not heat like chicken poo'

The phrase shaped *bèklagèèkmanôksu* clause is a phrase that is so popularly used. The meaning of this phrase cannot be understood by understanding the word per word because basically, every dirt is hot because it just came out of the body. However, the heat is only brief. The outside air (nature) lowers the temperature on the dirt. The purpose of this phrase is someone do not like dirt, his spirits only briefly. Spirit or enthusiasm must be constantly on fire so that when doing something it is not easy to give up, discourage, or retreat before arriving at the finish line.

The phrase serves to convey that in doing something we must be serious, diligent, and patient. In addition, one does not give up easily. This phrase is suitable for indirect use of others. Usually, the innuendo's innuendo will be offended and the awareness is only temporary. It is different when being insulted with the phrase, not easily offended and intent in and scarcely in mind. Therefore, the function of this phrase is directive because it can be used to influence others. The function of this directive is oriented to the message recipient to influence others by reminding, commanding, ordering, reminding, threatening, and so on.

The main problem in this research lies in the existence of the Acehnese expression which is becoming increasingly eliminated in Aceh society. In fact, the expression is a wealth of culture and local wisdom in Aceh. Phrases or idioms are linguistic units of words, phrases, or sentences whose meanings cannot be drawn from general or unpredictable rules of lexical meaning to the elements that make up them in a language (Rambitan and Mandolang, 2014). The phrase is a word or group of words specifically used to express an intent with figurative language. Similarly, it is argued that phrases are combinations of words extracted from long sentences. Thus, the phrase is a word that expresses a meaning from a specific intention with figurative language and contains values in society and is passed down from generation to generation (Danandjaja, 1986).

The Acehnese, both the Acehnese speakers and the Indonesian speaking community, often use the Acehnese expression when communicating. Speakers of the

Indonesian language obtain an Acehnese expression of the communication process with speakers of Aceh. Then, they use the phrase to emphasize and consolidate an understanding of something being delivered. As a means of strengthening the sense or meaning of communication about a context is often used the relevant phrase, as "seasoning flavor", especially the phrases that are based on the references (Azwardi, 2013).

In the current reality, the Acehnese phrase continues to receive the attention of the people of Aceh as it is still relevant to the context of the life of the people of Aceh today, although the phrases are not all known by Indonesian speakers in Aceh. Therefore, the study of this phrase is an attempt to see the expressions used by Indonesian speakers in Aceh.

The people of Aceh have "weapons" in the language, whether they are used as educating, insinuating, or counseling tools so-called phrases. The phrase is as a people's policy that is one's intelligence. Expressions are short sentences extracted from long experiences (Danandjaja, 1986). The phrases and proverbs share the same concept. This is because the maxim is a concise, compact phrase that contains comparison, parables, counsel, life principle or rules of conduct (Kridalaksana, 2008).

The phrase is part of the communication of the cultural system of society (Geertz, 1964). Of course the expressions that grow in society are positive. The values contained in these phrases consist of conceptions that live in the minds of society and are considered very noble because they are also considered to be guides in attitude, speech and behavior. The phrase function includes (1) the thickening of religious emotions or beliefs; (2) educational tools; (3) an acceptable explanation of common sense; and (4) entertainer (Danandjaja, 1986).

Sociolinguistics comes from the words "socio" and "linguistic". Socio is the same as social word that is related to society. Linguistics is the science that studies and speaks the language especially the elements of language. Thus, sociolinguistics is a study of theories about the relationship of society to language (Nababan, 1993). Sociolinguistics focuses on the social groups as well as the linguistics used in the group while attempting to correlate these linguistic elements with traditional demographic units on the social sciences, namely: age, gender, socioeconomic class, regional grouping, status and others. Even in recent days there has also been a correlation between linguistic forms and social functions in intra communal interaction for the delivery of desired things. It is also defined as the study of how social norms and values influence linguistic behavior; variety and variety are connected with the social framework of its speakers; and the utilization of political linguistic resources as well as social aspects of bilingualism (Alwashilah, 1993).

Therefore, sociolinguistics puts the language in relation to its wearer in society. This means that sociolinguistics views language as primarily a social system and communication system. Sociolinguistics provides a guide and ordinance to speakers in using the language, be it a variety of languages or styles of language that must be applied when communicating.

The phrases and proverbs share the same concept. This is because the maxim is a concise, compact phrase that contains comparison, parables, counsel, life principle or rules of conduct (Kridalaksana, 1999). The phrase is as a people's policy that is one's intelligence. The expression is the phonological or grapheme aspect of the language element that supports the meaning (Kridalaksana, 1999). In this regard, phrasing is a short sentence extracted from long experience (Danandjaja, 1986).

Furthermore, the phrase may also be interpreted as a word or group of words specifically used for an intent with the figurative meanings spoken as softly as possible and easily understood. They argue that the expression is born from the experiences of one's life and translated as something that has value in view and mind, then be able to transform (transmitted) to others.

The function of phrase is as a thickening of religious emotion or belief, as a collective imaginary projections derived from the hallucination of a person who is experiencing mental disorders in the form of supernatural beings, as educational tools of children or adolescents, as an explanation that can acceptable common sense, and to entertain people who are experiencing disaster.

The features of expression are as follows.

1. Contains figurative meaning;
2. Consists of a group of words, phrases, or sentences;
3. Contains values and functions for life, social, morals, and others;
4. The particular feature of the Aceh phrase begins with the word *lagèe* (Tarigan 1985).

Marking a phrase can be seen from its characteristics. Based on the characteristics of the phrase can be distinguished by poem or proverb. Thus, based on the characteristics expressed by Tarigan di above, the phrase can be categorized based on its characteristics.

2. Method

This study used descriptive qualitative method. How it works by describing the object of research and examine the elements contained in the object of the study. Technique of collecting data is done by interview and note to informant. The immediate informant is determined by the researcher or the recommendation of another person who is considered often use the phrase in everyday communication so that the expression data is filtered at the source. The data have been obtained will be analyzed qualitatively and described in the form of descriptive.

3. Results and Discussion

- (1) *Lagèe* beans *tuwekeukulet*
'As peanuts forget their skin'

The phrase (1) contains a function. The function of this phrase is about the critique of sociology. The value of this criticism is illustrated so clearly that the opposite is implied, ie the peanut shell forgotten on the skin. This phrase is usually used by informants to criticize the unfaithfulness of someone. When there are others on our side to help, protect, care, and guide, we must not forget the service. In terms of function, phrase (1) can be a "weapon" in educating, counseling, or reminding others. This expression is precisely targeted to people who are not loyal or forget the services of others. Moreover, the specifics of this phrase can be used as a whip in the insinuation of those who behave as described above.

(2) *Raya patè asam dengonpate bu*

'Great place for a side dish rather than a rice place'

Commonly, bowl of rice is greater than other bowls. However, what is described in the phrase (*raya patè asam dengonpate bu*) is different. This shows that there is a side touched by this expression either to educate, quip, or remind. In spite of all this, the function of this phrase is similar to the proverb "do not be big pegs from the pole" or "do not spend bigger than income". In addition to counseling, phrase (3) becomes very useful when used for self-introspection in doing something. Moreover, we do not occasionally prioritize circumcision rather than mandatory or prioritize secondary and tertiary needs rather than primary needs. That is the function of the above expression. In essence, this life must be balanced so peaceful, peaceful, and affluent. In the realm of function, this phrase serves as an advice to those who put their passions on the spot. In tune with the "great appetite of lack of energy" this expression is a whip for such people.

(3) *Lagèè overpass putohtalo*

'Like a broken rope'

Layang-layang (kite) will fly in the air without direction because the controller no longer exists. That is, everything must be based on laws, rules, or systems so that everything is orderly. *Layang-layang* is an object that can be flown when windy in a large field or paddy field by using yarn as its controller. If you want to fly close to the surface then the thread rolled and vice versa. It is conceivable what would happen if it was broken from the overpass. This phrase serves as an expression of advice in communication. The breadth of the scope of the intentions contained in it can be implemented in everyday life so that it becomes an expression of counsel.

(4) *Bak gunongbèktakambakgunong*

'On the mountain do not add mountains'

Growing an attitude of justice and eliminating greed is the function of expression (4). Two things can be seen from the use of the word "mountain". Mountain in the above phrase is meant with many treasures. On the one hand this phrase describes greed. About these two things is important in society. The presence of phrases intended for justice and greed can at least be used as a carrier of good values in order to improve human degrees. The power of value about the prohibition of not adding to the treasures so spontaneously is said. Therefore, the above expression serves as educational / educational.

(5) *Bèklagèèkmanòksuùm*

'Do not heat like dirt.'

Basically, every dirt is hot because it just came out of the body. However, the heat is only briefly. The outside air (nature) lowers the temperature on the dirt. This is what is expected of this phrase. More precisely, the expression (5) says we do not like dirt, the heat is only brief. Spirit or enthusiasm must be constantly burning on our minds so that when doing something is not easy to give up, discourage, or retreat

before arriving at the finish line. The function of the expression (2) may include all sides of which are as follows.

- a. This expression teaches anyone to do something to be serious, diligent, and patient.
- b. People who give up easily are the characteristics of people who dare like chicken droppings because it easily wilt, discouraged, and pessimistic.
- c. This phrase is suitable for indirect use of others.

(6) Manyangiedengonitèk
'High water rather than duck'

The intent in an expression may vary. This difference is caused by the interpretation of the meaning of a phrase by each person of different uses. This expression can be used in accordance with the capacity of the intentions it contains. Determination of a function in the expression can be seen from its use, the expression (6) its use is more in the direction for the cultivation of value for others who behave: the large expenditure of the income; work not in accordance with capacity; and excessive appearance. Thus it can be deduced that the function of this phrase as conveying the value of kindness in others.

(7) Lagèe camat gadoh stamp
'Like camat lost stamp'

Lagèe clamp stamp is the expression of the situation. All elements of society go into it, from ordinary people, geuchik, camat, regents, governors, to the highest level, the president. Seals are office equipment to certify a letter. These two things cannot be separated. The connection is so close. A busy person's situation is imbued with Camat (Head of District). The function of this phrase depends on its meaning. When the purpose of this phrase is said simply to joke with colleagues, then its function becomes entertainment. This phrase can also serve as an allusion. In one moment there are people who busy are not clear, panic is also not appropriate situation, this is the right expression affixed to people who behave so. However, in addition to these two functions, the *lagèe* of the sub-district head of the seal contains a moral message that in every situation we must remain calm, focused, and meticulous in various ways, so that the tasks and work load we do will be perfect.

(8) *Lagèe* flies mirah rung
'Like red flies'

Through the expression of social ills can be treated slowly. Its value and message will touch the instincts of speakers and listeners so that awareness will be improved gradually as well. The function of *lagèe* fly expressions to teach how big the risks of people who behave like flies. Her sheep action will harm others. It is hoped that this phrase can deliver the value of kindness through communications that gradually touch the hearts of the listener. Not only listeners, speakers must be a role model for liver disease (sheep) disappeared from this world.

(9) *Lagèe*boh pineungteupup two

'As the nut is halved'

The phrase (7) is a group of words to describe a perfectly harmonious couple. Lagèboh pineungteupup two is the right expression intended for a matching couple. Not just limited to the portrayal of harmony only. A deeper study that everyone has advantages and disadvantages. The good couple should be able to deal with the weaknesses of his partner with the advantages that exist in him so that there will be a friendship, brotherhood, or a lasting marriage as long as the body is still contained. It cannot be denied that the nature of moral messages will lead us to a wiser, polite, and wise in addressing things. It can be concluded that the function of expression (9) contains two things, namely as a tool for praise and life guidance.

(10) Lagèemiedengontikoh
'Like a cat with a mouse'

The story of the feud of rats and cats has since both existed on this earth. Why is that, because in the food chain, rats are a delicious food of cat. However, the cunning, agility, and speed of mice shy away from their prey makes the cat upset. The story of the two feuds is also depicted in a cartoon film that essentially they will continue to quarrel. The meaning of this phrase is precisely aimed at people who are just like mice and cats. Never get along and always quarrel. Wider scope, this dispute will lead to hostilities and will take victims to trigger the emergence of disputing groups. This expression wants to say that such attitudes have been overcome by lust and harming everyone.

The function of this phrase can be used as a whip to cultivate forgiveness. In disagreement, a person has been overcome by lust and jinn. Without a wise solution if two things that have dominated humans in various ways. Thus, through this phrase it is expected to avoid disputes, hostilities, and quarrels that create negative effects.

(11) The warfare is as fine as ever
'Temperament like parasite tree'

Cooperation benefits both parties, while dependency only benefits one party and the other side will continue to lose. This is the description of the expression (11). Want to be appreciated by others, so keep the temperament like parasite. The parrot is carried by a bird to a tree and inhabits the tree. The residence makes other plants lose because parasite absorbs food from the tree until the branch where it sticks to death. This will be a social disease that causes people to distance us. The expression guides people not to behave thus. Therefore, in accordance with its function, the expression (11) invites the character to be discarded from an early age. Furthermore, the negative effects that appear are not half-hearted. If the plants, the branch will die. If in humans, trigger the emergence of disunity and quarrels.

(12) Beklagèelamji-e
'Do not be like in the *tampi*'

The phrase (12) expresses man with no direction and purpose in life. Life planning is not arranged in such a way that it is not well directed. The lesson that can

be learned from this phrase function is that life must be well planned. *Tampi* is a tool for removing rice from dirt (rock, rice, etc.) made from bamboo and widely used by mothers. *Tampi* shape oval and the back side is larger than the front. In it does not come, but it is more curved inward so that if there is contents in it he will dock into the middle. With a width of about one meter wide, the contents in the *tampi* will roll over like a human in the middle of Adang sand. The function of this phrase as a deliberate portrayal of life. Through the phrase, several things can be done so that the intended intent of the speaker is implied. This expression teaches its speakers to be wiser in the use of time. That is, the time is spent on a path that is pleasing to God.

(13) *LagèebrijukbeukahBoh*
'Like birds breaking eggs'

Fuss is a form of anger thrown by way of treatment or conversation and done to someone else. In addition, he may also be expressed as a sense of dissatisfaction towards something because he did not achieve his goals and satisfaction. Unfulfilled desires are also a major factor in this attitude. Being a nag is good and bad. The good will be upon the master of the body and the bad go to the people around. But this situation depends. If people around him are also kind of chatty or no story, surely he will not feel troublesome. But if the forefront with different individuals whose character is more relaxed, the nags will be seen annoying. The essence of the sari that can serve as a function of this phrase is that a fussy person will not realize he is fussy, but the people around who are usually the victims of incessant cynical and ignorant words.

(14) *Glulagèeaneuk arrow*
'Slip like jackfruit seed'

The phrase (14) contains a broad meaning. The purpose of this phrase-shaped phrase is to insinuate because the proactive is meant to be negative and that attitude interferes with the comfort of others. Therefore, this phrase is appropriate to educate, insult, and offend others indirectly because the meaning is very suitable.

In line with the meaning, this expression serves to educate, insinuate, and offend others and yourself. Do not act erratically so that others are not comfortable with our behavior. Likewise others who behave unwise that fit the phrase *glulagèeaneuk* arrows. So the function of this phrase is more directed to the character education aspect in order to give a positive influence for the surrounding community.

(15) *Lagèeklahdeungonpilek*
'Like *klah* with *patarana*'

Klah is a tool used to squeeze the coconut that has been decomposed in order to take the oil. Coconuts that have been squeezed out of oil will become *patarana*. Relationship *klah* with *pataranan* is very close. Both are there to remove the oil which is then used as cooking oil. The depiction of *klah* with *pataranan* in this phrase is a manifestation of strong friendship. The bonding of two objects to produce something for others is shown in this phrase. The purpose of this phrase leads to friendship. Cooking oil is the result of *klah* and *pataranan*.

This phrase shows the two things combined to produce one other thing that is beneficial to human survival. This is what is taught through the function of this phrase about friendship. With friends is expected to combine creative ideas or social action in order to provide enlightenment in a positive direction for others. Not only that, let alone for others, useful for both is more than enough.

(16) *Lagèinonggeutaleuk makmeugang* night
'Like the night-bomber seized'

Meugang is a celebration before the fast and the feast, whether it is Idul Adha or Idul Fitri. On *meugang*, women (wives) should cook meat brought home by their husbands. Something despicable if a woman is divorced at this time. This habit will bring down the dignity of the woman herself and her family. Thus this phrase was born with the intention of stating that it is not good for both women and men. The red thread of this phrase refers more to moral education in order to become a virtuous and character man. Of course every phrase has a function. Every expression is present in society with their respective functions.

This phrase is in the form of clauses and serves as a guideline and self-control so as not to absorb. For a woman crown, one of them, is her speech. They will be very graceful when politely communicates, the election is regular, and the quality of the speech is well preserved so that many men are amazed at it. In addition, the way speech represents the way of thinking.

(17) *Lagèeaneukhanama*
'Like no mother'

For a mother and child when it has been "gifted" this phrase will be devastated. This blow is a very crude satire. Children get guidance from parents. Parents are obliged to educate a child. Both have a very close relationship. The role of parents determines the future of the child. Morally children usually get well guided. The purpose of the above expression is directed at parents who do not guard, guide, and care for their children. The use of the child and mother in this phrase affirms the purpose that the quality of family guidance (mother, father, etc.) determines the quality of the child forward.

The phrase function (17) is clause-shaped and leads to the parent's obligation to guide the child until the age of the child. Children should be well cared for to be a figure of integrity and character. With parenting guidance and education the child will grow well.

Sociolinguistics examines language by taking into account the relationship between language and society, especially the language speakers. Each speaker has its own purpose when communicating. That means one of them will be seen from the language he uses when speaking. Language as a tool in the phrase can lead to various things for human survival.

Language as a tool in the phrase can lead to various things for human survival. The phrase is still developing with short sentences extracted from long experience. The phrase can be used as a word. This group of words is specifically used to usher in meanings with the figurative meanings spoken as softly as possible and easily understood. The phrase born based on the experiences of one's life and translated as

something that has value in view and mind, then be able to transform (transmitted) to others.

The findings of expression at the study sites varied widely. In terms of purpose, the whole phrase must be understood and correlated with everyday experience because it is often interpreted in deeper meaning than what appears at a glance. The meaning in the phrase is implicit. The wholeness of meaning is implied behind the words and parables used.

One of the advantages of meaning in expression when one value can be used in various things, for example, the value of education. Education as value here is not narrow in the scope of teaching and learning, but its scope to the family order, nature, society, and even to the natural phenomenon that phenomenon is beneficial to society such as the phenomenon of rain. So deep is the meaning in the expression.

The phrase means loyalty, justice, tranquility, life balance, harmony, greed, social criticism, dependency, education, friendship, guidance, and counsel. Of all these intentions it is not as general as it is mentioned. That is every expression is very specific and leads to the thing desired by the speaker in his communication. The phrase *lagèe tuwekeukulet* means that intend loyalty, but if done in-depth study on this phrase will be found intent in terms of functioning from faithful it is shown from forgetting the services of others.

4. Conclusion

The existence of the Acehese expression in the culture of the Indonesian speaking community is evolving with short sentences extracted from long experience. This phrase serves as a tool for educating, insinuating, social criticism, counseling, and so on that have a positive nature. The function of the expression is closely related to the value of taste. This taste value appears in a word / lexeme that can distinguish the meaning of denotative and connotative meanings.

The complexity of the expression of connotative and denotative meanings makes Indonesian speakers must be very careful in choosing the phrase in their communication. This is because the interpretation of meaning for each phrase is different. This distinction makes different functions as well. The phrase exegesis in communication is very diverse. It may exist in terms of loyalty, justice, tranquility, life balance, harmony, greed, social criticism, dependence, education, friendship, guidance, or counsel.

The phrase as a cultural richness is a cultural treasure that deserves to be preserved. Its preservation because of the Acehese phrase has a certain function in society so that the expression is used when communicating. The functions are diverse in order to establish loyalty, fairness, tranquility, and maintain a balance of life. The Acehese phrase exists in the Indonesian speaking community because it has a continuity between communication and its implementation in community life. The existence of this phrase is used as a social critique, guidance, and advice to strengthen unity and unity within the framework of Indonesian culture. This expression exists for speakers of the Indonesian language because it contains the power of value that is able to educate speakers unconsciously and thoroughly.

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Syntactical interference of Katingan language to Indonesian language in SMP Negeri 1 at Katingan Tengah regency of Central Kalimantan

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Abstract – Syntactical interference of Language of Katingan to Indonesian in Katingan Tengah School at Katingan Tengah regency has been a focus of some language research recently. The research was aimed at recognizing and identifying interference in second language acquisition. The term interference refers to two different linguistic phenomena, namely psychological interference and sociolinguistic interference. Psychological interference refers to the influence of old habits as a result of learning something against something being studied (Rafiek, 2007). While sociolinguistic interference refers to the interaction of the language, such as loan or word change. Factors that cause interference is the factor of contact language and language skills. Interference is caused by language contact factors in bilingual societies and an unsteady language mastery factor in second language learners or foreign language learners (Rafiek, 2009). This is in accordance with the teacher's opinion that there are still errors in the language, whether it's talking and writing activities. That's what makes researchers interested in doing this. Based on the above problems, it can be identified some points, namely the influence of the first language habit of Katingan in using a second language, Indonesian language, language skills that have not been steady in the second language learning and errors in the language, because of the influence of the first language. The result of research on the syntactic interference aspects of Katingan language to Indonesian language was found in two types of syntactic interference which was contained in oral and written language of students of SMPN 1 Katingan Tengah, such as (1) Interference phrase to Indonesian language and (2) Interference sentence to Indonesian language.

Keywords: *interference, morphology, Katingan language, oral, writing*

1. Introduction

Indonesia has many languages, therefore Indonesian people are bilingual. This can be seen with the use of two languages in communicating. In addition to mastering the Indonesian language as the national language, they also mastered their respective local languages. Both languages are sometimes used simultaneously in certain situations and conditions. This phenomenon affects the ability of one to use a language due to the language contact. Not only Indonesia which has its language diversity, Dayak tribe in Kalimantan also has various regional languages. One of the regional languages found in Central Kalimantan is Katingan, whose name was chosen because its speakers live along the river Katingan.

Language is a communication tool that can be used by a person to express ideas that will be poured in his mind. The expression of the language is to describe the state of the person or the speaker. Language is one of the most distinctive features of humanity that distinguishes it from other beings. Language can be studied from several angles and pay special attention to the different elements of language and to the discriminating (structure) relationships (Rafiek, 2010). Language is "an arbitrary system of symbolic sounds, used by members of a society to cooperate, interact, and self-identify", while the narrative according is a discourse that features a series of events within a certain time series, along with participants and specific circumstances (Yanti, 2011).

Given the variations of the language there was a bilingual or multilingual community phenomenon resulting from the contact of language as well as cultural contact. With the existence of a bilingual society, interference was then occurred. Interference is the transfer of other language elements into the language that is being used, so that there is a deviation of the rules of the language being used (Rafiek, 2010).

Interference comes from the researcher's finding that is a linguistic interaction that arises when two language societies make a language contact ^[5]. The interference is a deviation of the linguistic norms that appear in a bilingual person using one of two languages controlled in real communication. In harmony with the interference put forward, Rafiek (2010) defines interference as the difficulty that arises in the process of acquiring a second language in terms of sound, word, or construction as a result of differences in habit with the first language.

At first, interference was only divided into two, namely systemic interference and development interference. Systemic interference is the interference that occurs due to speaker language performance resulting in a change in the language system in which interference occurs. While development interference is the interference that occurs in the development of one's learning when learning a first language or learning a second language. This interference is also called learning interference (Rafiek, 2010). If we notice, interference that occurs in a language has advantages and disadvantages. Advantages of interference by speakers of language are, among others, can increase the vocabulary of the vocabulary and also enrich the language in question. Losses caused by interference by speakers of the language is able to affect and disrupt the structure, so that in its use occurs the language deviation.

The disadvantages of interferences by language speakers or also called negative transfers are known as interference terms in the acquisition of a second language. The term interference refers to two different linguistic phenomena, namely

psychological interference and sociolinguistic interference. Psychological interference refers to the influence of old habits as a result of learning something against something being studied (Rafiek, 2007). While sociolinguistic interference refers to the interaction of the language, such as loan or password change.

Factors that cause interference is the factor of contact language and language skills. Interference is caused by language contact factors in bilingual societies and an unsteady language mastery factor in second language learners or foreign language learners (Rafiek, 2007). This is in accordance with the field, namely the opinion of teachers that there are still errors in the language, whether it's talking and writing activities. That's what makes researchers interested in doing this. Examples of errors that occur due to Katingan language interference, which was found during writing activities of Indonesian language. "I'm very happy to see the rice planted me and the mother has been *manguning*". The word *manguning* here due to Katingan language interference that does not recognize the letter /e/. Should in Indonesian become yellow. Another example is the word *manugal* should be *menugal*.

2. Method

The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative method. Descriptive qualitative methods are appropriate for understanding social interaction and can only be described if researchers conduct research by participating, in-depth interviews of social interaction. So, it can be said this research method in collecting or providing data and analyze data to study the phenomenon of language that happened. Thus, this research uses descriptive research methods that have several characteristics, such as (1) not blaming true or wrong object studied, (2) emphasis on actual symptoms or on what happened at the time of the research, and (3) usually not directed to test the hypothesis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Interference aspects of syntax

Interference in the field of syntax is also found in the use of the Indonesian language. The use of word fragments, phrases, and clauses in sentences can also be said to be interference at the sentence level.

(1) Phase Interference

Data 1

Arriving at Makikit I am also excited by not being patient I can park my bike and invite my friends to walk towards the cascade. It turns out that many people kamipun queue to walk there because many vacation there. The use of the suffixes is used as a pronoun which states ownership that is combined with the word base. Aside from being a possession pronoun, the ending also serves to show something. In the student's writing above, in the second sentence there are phrases turned out to be

people, there are language errors due to the influence of Katingan language. It should improve the sentence below.

Arriving at Makikit I also am excited by not being patient I can park my bike and invite my friends to walk towards the cascade. It turns out that many visitors we also queue to walk there, because many vacation there.

(2) Sentence Interference

Data 2

Mother and I went to the fields, in the fields where we were both bemalam. Based on the above sentence, the interference done by the students in their writing is the use in the field there. The influence of the use of regional languages, i.e. in the fields of hecene into the fields there is a mistake in the Indonesian language. So, it can be said that the field already shows the place, without adding the word there. The correction of the sentence was me and mother going to the fields, in our fields both of us staying overnight.

Data 3

On the trip I almost fell off the motorcycle, because mehindari hole because the road to Makikit damaged almost 3 times I want to fall, luckily I can control it. On the journey almost 2 hours, we just got to Makikit from Samba and it's already our rate. Based on the student's writing above there is a language error that is in the second sentence, there is the use of our rate already. It should have been at high speed.

Data 4

Taking a bath we walked to the edge to relax while viewing the scenery, because over time sitting on the edge I will invite one of my friends to walk around us gathered, after getting to our gathering place two friends see our other friends have no us to the parking and rushed to return. Based on the above article there is a language error due to the imprint in word two should be both. The rest of the sentence should be finished After our bath walk to the edge to relax while looking at the scenery, because later sitting on the edge I will invite one of my friends to walk around us gathered, after to the gathering we both my friends see our other friends are not there we even went to the car park and hurry to go home.

Data 5

My appearance began to change and I always wanted to play games I subtracted although not completely lost, Based on the student's writing there is a word change is the use of the wrong word. The word is not derived from the fox base, but rather change. Interference that occurs is the use of the word change. So, it should be changed to change rather than change.

Data 6

One day fitting the holidays, the clock shows at 07.00 pm me and mother went to the fields. The above sentence is a fitting word, a holiday fitting day. The use of the word pas is the interference made by the students. Word does not exist in KBBI. Pas

defined when by students. So, fix the sentence as below. One day when the holidays, the clock shows at 07.00 pm me and mother went to the fields.

Data 7

Hau, do not be us with Sita. In that sentence seen the use of interjection in the use of Indonesian language. Interaction is the expression of feelings, the expression of a person when saying. Interjection is one of interference that occurs in students of SMPN 1 Katingan Tengah. Interjection is a fragment of the mother tongue that entered in the Indonesian language. Such rules are an aberration to the language used. The interjections found in addition to the above data are as below.

Data 8

Admit, the number of tasks today. May me Sita. The use of the word acknowledged in the speech illustrates the expression of the speaker's feeling. The word acknowledged and may be an interchange of Katingan. It can be said that the students' speech SMPN 1 Katingan Tengah is the interference due to the influence of the first language / mother.

Data 9

I love to have good friends, funny, silly, and so on in class VII D this. My friends are very the best deh. Based on the above data there is a flake that comes from English, namely the best. The flakes are interference at the sentence level. The data is a language deviation undertaken by junior high school students by incorporating other language systems into the language currently in use, i.e. Indonesian. In addition, similar interference is also found in student writing as below.

Data 10

After I rested until 03:00 we gathered again on our beskem. Based on the sentence in the student's writing, students deliberately use another word fragment, namely beskem. The use of the word beskem is an English flake, which should be the base camp. Other language systems that enter into the above sentences result in interference in the Indonesian language.

Data 11

Glad to see people go up to the kelotok, there are also people who are fishing, marengge, and bathing. Based on the writings of students above there are pieces of words derived from the Katingan language. The use of marengge is a mother language interference. Marengge is one way to catch fish by using a net stretched with bamboo, then drowned into the river and after it is lifted. Lacking and ignorance of Indonesian vocabulary results in interference in Katingan. The existence of the first language fragments in the use of the second language is a language error made by junior high school students.

Data 12

My hands keep writing. The same is also found in the above sentence. The use of word or word fragments derived from the first language is used in the use of a

second language. This results in interference in the Indonesian language. The use of the word pass is syntactic interference in Indonesian. The equivalent of the word pass in Indonesian is tingling. Improvement of the above sentence is Ouch my hand tingling pen continue.

Data 13

We went home, the journey is very cheerful, but there are snakes that again cross the road. From the writings of students there is a word *menyebarkan* in the Indonesian language is a language deviation due to the influence of the mother tongue. The basic word is opposite and given the prefix. The word begins s so that when given the prefix will melt. The use of mother tongue fragments to make this sentence found interference. The basic word forbidding is any, so when it is given the prefix becomes split. In the use of the Indonesian language, the word should be crossed. Repair the sentence as below. We went home very cheerful journey but there is a snake who again crossed the road.

4. Conclusion

Syntactic interference is a disorder that occurs due to the deviation of sentence structure. Based on the results of the analysis, two types of syntactic interference are found in the spoken and written language of SMPN 1 Katingan Tengah students, among others: (1) Phrase interference with Indonesian language and (2) Interference of sentence to Indonesian language.

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